

Health Data Science

Black

Internship

Programme Review

An independent review of the
programme by Advance HE

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To assess the Black Internship Programme (BIP) after its first four years (2021 - 2024), Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) commissioned Advance HE to undertake an independent evaluation. The purpose of this external review was to provide a transparent, evidence-led appraisal of the programme's design, delivery and outcomes.

The review was conducted against a clear set of objectives established by HDR UK at the commissioning stage. These were to:

1. Evaluate the programme's design and implementation, including engagement with applicants and host organisations;
2. Determine whether the BIP has delivered its intended outputs and outcomes;
3. Assess the programme's value and influence on HDR UK and the wider health data science sector;
4. Generate recommendations to inform the scope and delivery of future iterations of the programme.

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Foreword

When opportunity is created, talent flourishes

The power of health data science is transformational. It holds the key to understanding disease, improving care, and creating a healthier, fairer future for everyone.

However, if the people shaping the future don't represent the society it is built to serve, our science will be weaker, our responses narrower, and the benefits of innovation more unevenly distributed. The true value of data rests on who gathers it, who interprets it, and who is trusted to turn insight into action.

Five years ago, we chose to act. The Black Internship Programme (BIP) was our response - a practical, targeted intervention to tackle the systemic underrepresentation of Black people across science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) and particularly within health data science.

The BIP set out not just to place interns, but to build futures. It offers paid, meaningful experience, technical training, mentoring, and community for Black students and graduates. In doing so, it strengthens the entire ecosystem.

We invited Advance HE to take an independent look at what this programme has achieved in its first four years. Their findings are unequivocal.

The BIP works. Host organisations gain fresh perspectives, new skills, and a tangible way to act on their commitments to diversity. Interns gain confidence, networks, and access to opportunities that change lives. Both sides learn, grow, and succeed.

The review brings to life the lived experience of interns, the shifts in host organisations as well as the strengthened commitment across the sector to doing better.

More importantly, the review shows the way forward - practical steps to deepen impact, broaden partnerships and embed sustainable practice.

We are immensely proud of the progress documented in this report and deeply grateful to every intern, host, and supporter who has made the BIP what it is today.

Our work, however, is far from done. This review should not be seen as a conclusion but as a call to action. Scale what works, sustain what matters and ensure the next generation of health data scientists is as diverse and dynamic as the challenges they will solve.

Professor Martin Levermore

Chair, Health Data Science Black Internship Programme Advisory Group
Health Data Research UK

Professor Andrew Morris

Director
Health Data Research UK

Executive summary

It is acknowledged that racial bias currently exists within health data and data-driven technology ([Gibney, 2022](#); [Knight et al., 2021](#)), partly driven by under-representation of Black people working in the sector, which risks exacerbating health inequalities. This is also a factor in the ‘leaky pipeline’ – career paths with a decrease in representation at each level, resulting in fewer individuals reaching senior positions – of Black people in science, technology, engineering and maths (STEM), as well as health science disciplines in academia ([Williams et al., 2019](#)).

Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) launched its Black Internship Programme (BIP) in 2021, primarily as an initiative to address these inequities in health data science and to provide support for Black people to enter the sector. More broadly, it aims to help improve inequities in health data and ultimately in health outcomes, that are perpetuated by an under-representative workforce.

The programme, delivered in partnership with the [10,000 Interns Foundation](#) and the [UK Health Data Research Alliance](#), facilitates paid work experience for future Black data scientists. Interns are placed

for 8 weeks over the summer period in one of the many host organisations who partake in the programme every year, and also receive a programme of training and networking opportunities alongside their placement.

The key purpose of this review is to evaluate HDR UK’s BIP between its inception and 2024 (2021-2024). Specifically, the review aims to evaluate the programme’s approach to engaging the target internship audience and host organisations, determine whether it has achieved its intended outputs and outcomes, explore its value and influence on HDR UK and the wider health data science sector and generate recommendations for the next iterations of the programme.

A multi-stage, mixed-methods approach was adopted for this programme evaluation, consisting of development of a Theory of Change, a desk-based review, and stakeholder consultation, engaging alumni (former interns who took part in the programme), host organisation staff, HDR UK staff, BIP advisory board members and wider sector experts.

Summary of findings

Between 2021-2024, 308 interns participated in the BIP, working with 98 host organisations. The review finds that BIP is a successful, impactful programme for both interns and host organisations, improving access for more diverse talent to enter the sector. The programme has built a reputation as an intervention combating the under-representation of Black people in health data science through the provision of a holistic, supportive curriculum. The exponential growth in applications for places on the programme in recent years is testament to the value it holds for aspiring Black health data scientists.

- + 43% of alumni survey respondents went on to either work or further study in health data science, health technology or data science, after completing the programme. Importantly, most alumni directly attribute their entry into the sector to their participation in the programme, whilst host organisations agree that interns are more 'job-ready' on completion of the programme
- + Reported satisfaction with the programme was extremely high, both amongst interns and host organisations
- + The programme's structured and holistic approach, as well as the quality of support received from the BIP project team are highly-rated aspects of the programme. Interns also highlight the opportunity to work on a real-world research topic, the valuable networking and mentorship opportunities, and their positive experiences with supervisors and managers
- + Alumni praise the BIP as a transformative experience, enhancing both their technical and non-technical skills, whilst also building their confidence to pursue a career in the sector

- + Host organisation staff report benefitting from the opportunity to get access and contribute to the development of a more diverse workforce. They also report improved understanding of the barriers faced by Black people in the sector and greater insight into how to shape inclusive recruitment and wider working practices, whilst acknowledging the quality of the interns
- + Both alumni and host organisations would highly recommend the programme to their respective peers

Despite the largely positive findings across the programme, from a diverse group of stakeholders, there are a number of areas for further consideration.

- + Demand in the programme from applicants grew exponentially in 2024. However, turn-over of host organisations is high, with hosts typically only staying in the programme for 1-2 cycles. This has not enabled growth in available internships to meet the rise in demand
- + To date, the lean programme team have been highly effective in delivering a high-quality, impactful programme. However, at times the team capacity is stretched, and this limits the opportunity to expand the programme beyond its current size, should this be desirable in the future
- + Accessibility of datasets for both the technical challenge and internship projects is challenging
- + Some interns found management of the group dynamics and skills mix for the technical challenge, difficult
- + Some stakeholders would welcome the programme to support other under-represented groups, not just Black people

43% of alumni survey respondents went on to either work or further study in health data science, health technology or data science, after completing the programme.

Based on the evidence gathered through this review, we present the following four recommendations for shaping the programme's future:

- 1. Co-design the next phase of the programme with key stakeholders**
- 2. Whilst remaining lean, expand the delivery team's capacity and increase the resilience of the host organisation pipeline**
- 3. Strengthen external communications to further promote the programme's impact and clarify the host organisation offer**
- 4. Continue to focus on feedback, monitoring and evaluation**

HDR UK's BIP occupies a unique space, delivering a bespoke, practical development curriculum in health data science, specifically for Black people to address their substantial under-representation in the sector. The impact of the programme is evident from the high proportion of its alumni who enter the sector, following its completion, and from the high regard with which the programme is held by its alumni, host organisations and the health data science community more broadly. At a time when the political climate surrounding the importance and value of diversity in our workplaces and for our health feels uncertain, the BIP has never been more needed. We hope the programme will take the findings from this evaluation and use them to fuel its progress for the next four years, and beyond.

1

Introduction and background context

Black people are heavily under-represented in the science, technology, engineering and maths (STEM) community ([Advance HE, 2023](#)) as well as within health data and data-driven technology ([Gibney, 2022](#); [Knight et al., 2021](#)). Data submitted by the Careers Research and Advisory Centre (CRAC) in the most recent [Science and Technology Committee's report on Diversity and Inclusion in STEM \(2023\)](#) show signs of attrition along the academic progression path of UK-domiciled Black scientists (see also [Williams et al., 2019](#)). Figure 1 below summarises the UK-domiciled Black scientists' population in UK Higher Education (HE) based on data provided in the 2023 CRAC report.

Black students in UK HE STEM subjects also receive poorer degree outcomes and lower rates of academic career progression compared to other ethnic groups ([Royal Society, 2021](#); [Advance HE, 2023](#)). Furthermore, intersectionality of diverse characteristics such as race and sex creates even more barriers; for example, for Black women specifically in academia ([WHEN Change for Good, 2025](#)). However, the issue of under-representation of minoritised groups in STEM

is not limited to academia, with disproportionate representation also reported among NHS staff ([WRES Implementation Team, 2020](#)) and among the boards of top UK tech firms ([The Lancet Digital Health, 2020](#)), for example.

Despite these challenges and recent changes in the political landscape regarding attitudes towards equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI), the importance of fostering diversity, nurturing inclusion and creating equitable working environments and cultures in the UK and worldwide is widely recognised. Focusing on the UK, funders and higher education institutions have intensified their attempts to embed EDI into their business as usual (for example, UKRI's new [EDI policy](#) and [funding data](#), Advance HE's [Race Equality Charter](#), etc), especially after the influence exerted by the Black Lives Matter movement and the relevant challenges posed to institutions and funders to actively show their commitment to anti-racism. Beyond the education sector, the UK Government recognises the importance of attracting people from all backgrounds into research and development (R&D)

Figure 1 / Progression pathway of UK-domiciled Black scientists in UK HE

to help it remain a pioneer in effectively addressing global challenges, such as the Covid-19 pandemic, and other complex problems. The 2021 R&D People and Culture Strategy acknowledged that if the UK research culture “is not seen as open and inclusive” it “puts off and drives out talent, preventing individuals from producing their very best work” ([Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, 2021](#)). Similarly, the UK Life Sciences industry has recognised the need to ensure a diverse workforce in order to meet its substantial skills demands and support future growth ([Science Industry Partnership, 2022](#)). This is because greater workplace diversity not only serves to broaden the pool of available talent, but it also enables the development of new technologies, fosters collaboration and delivers innovations. Finally, there is a productivity and economic aspect to the arguments that highlight the importance of EDI (see [Royal Academy of Engineering, 2025](#), for example), as it is now widely accepted that companies that attract and develop individuals from the widest pool of available talent consistently perform better ([Science Industry Partnership, 2022](#)).

In response to the mounting evidence of the under-representation of Black people in the STEM community, HDR UK decided to address this issue by launching its UK Black Internship Programme (BIP) in 2020, with its first cohort commencing in the summer of 2021.

1.1 / BIP – a brief overview

Run by HDR UK in partnership with the [10,000 Interns Foundation](#) and the [UK Health Data Alliance](#), the [Black Internship Programme](#) is aimed at addressing under-representation within the health data science sector by offering early-career Black data scientists the opportunity to carry out real-world practical projects, make industry connections, and get an insider’s perspective of what health data science careers look like. The programme is championed in the [Medical Research Council’s Strategic Delivery Plan 2022-25](#) as a way to develop a diverse research and technical workforce with the skills to address today’s innovation challenges.

The programme’s intended outputs and outcomes are as follows:

BIP's intended outputs

- + Provide health data science internship placements for Black students and graduates
- + Introduce Black students and graduates to health data science knowledge and practice
- + Create opportunities for Black students already studying or interested in health data science to gain experience in the field

BIP's intended outcomes

- + Raise awareness of the problem of racial bias within the health data science sector
- + Provide meaningful insight into career opportunities in health data science for Black interns
- + Encourage Black interns to consider health data science as a career
- + Change the approach of organisations working in health data science regarding recruitment and support of Black individuals
- + Establish HDR UK as a leader in advancing the careers of under-represented groups in health data science

The programme offers paid work experience to future Black data scientists, who are placed for 8 weeks over the summer period in one of the many host organisations who partake in the programme every year. The programme is a comprehensive offer, including the following:

- + 8-week paid internship at London Living Wage
- + Provision of a laptop for the duration of the internship, if required
- + Opportunities across various health data science sectors
- + A real-world health research project developed by each host organisation for its interns
- + Exclusive access to curated training resources as well as to training sessions every Friday afternoon
- + Customised learning pathway within [HDR UK Futures](#) online learning platform
- + Mentor and line manager for each intern
- + Team technical challenge and prize giving
- + Certificate recognising intern achievements
- + Networking with other interns and host organisation staff, including attendance of the programme's in-person Opening and Closing Ceremonies
- + Ongoing career support post-programme through Amazon Web Services (AWS) mentoring and the HDR UK Alumni Network
- + Opportunity for interns to join the wider 10,000 Black Interns community

1.2 / Purpose of this review

Evaluation is at the core of effective implementation of EDI considerations. Therefore, HDR UK commissioned Advance HE to evaluate BIP after its four years of operation. This independent review has been commissioned to address the following objectives:

- + Evaluate the programme design and implementation, including the approach to engaging the target internship audience and host organisations
- + Determine if the BIP has achieved its intended outputs and outcomes
- + Understand the programme's value to and influence on HDR UK and the wider health data science sector
- + Generate recommendations for the scope of the next iteration of the programme

This report consists of five remaining chapters. Chapter two focuses on the methodologies underpinning this review, outlining the multi-stage, mixed-methods approach adopted. Chapter three is devoted to presenting the findings of a desk-based review, conducted to highlight commonalities and differences between HDR UK's BIP and other relevant initiatives. Chapter four presents the findings of the primary data collection, outlining key elements from the online surveys, focus groups and interviews conducted alongside participants' recommendations for what future iterations of the BIP could look like. The final chapter ties all this evidence together, outlining insights related to BIP's process and impact evaluation, as well as some points for consideration for its future outlook.

2

Methodology

The key purpose of this review is to evaluate HDR UK's BIP between its inception and 2024 (2021-2024), from multiple angles. The main objectives of the review are listed above in section 1.2.

A multi-stage, mixed-methods approach was adopted as the best way to approach this programme evaluation, consisting of:

1. Developing a theory of change as the evaluation framework
2. A desk-based review
3. Stakeholder consultation

2.1 / Theory of Change development

Two Theory of Change (ToC) workshops were facilitated by Advance HE, consisting of an in-person workshop at the beginning of October 2024, followed by an additional online session towards the end of that month to gather additional input from a wider range of stakeholders. The two sessions were attended by a variety of participants, spanning programme leaders, advisory group members, host organisation staff as well as alumni. The outcome of these two workshops was a co-created ToC framework for the BIP, outlining the programme's aim, rationale, inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impact to establish a foundation for implementation and impact evaluation. The resulting framework can be accessed in the following page (see Figure 2 on the following page).

2.2 / Desk-based review

To build on the ToC foundation, we reviewed BIP documents and existing data (for example, engagement statistics, feedback survey data, publications of the programme's impact to date, etc) to create a descriptive analysis of the programme (numbers of participants and host organisations, demographics of participants, etc). Additionally, we compared the BIP to three similar initiatives, which we co-decided between the Advance HE team and the BIP review project team, using publicly available data to explore differences and similarities as well as potential opportunities for enhancing the BIP. Comparison programmes were selected based on similarities in sector of focus and under-represented groups targeted.

Figure 2 / BIP Theory of Change Framework

1				
Situation	<p>Black people’s underrepresentation increases the further up we progress in the academic ladder (leaky pipeline). Black people are also underrepresented amongst NHS staff and the wider health data science sector, particularly so at the senior leadership level. This underrepresentation is a result of structural and systemic issues (e.g. biases in recruitment, retention, promotion and progression, lack of meaningful mentorship and/or networks to enable access and participate in the sector etc.). The mounting evidence of the underrepresentation of Black people within the STEM community has been intensified by the sociopolitical context (E.g. Black Live Matters movement, Covid-19 pandemic and data showing the underfunding of Black scientists as well as the disproportionate effects of Covid on minoritised communities), with national and organisational policies acknowledging that attracting and including people from all backgrounds is essential to maintain the UK research and developments’ pioneer status in effectively addressing global challenges.</p>			
2				
Aims	<p>The Black Internship Programme (BIP) has been established to provide paid placement opportunities for Black students and recent graduates in STEM subjects in host organisations, which will allow them to gain meaningful insights to health data science. Through BIP, Black interns will be equipped and encouraged to consider pursuing a career in this field and the sector will have a job-ready talent pool to recruit from. Moreover, BIP aims to assist host organisations and the wider sector to understand how systemic and structural barriers (re)produce the underrepresentation of Black people within the health data science sector, and how they can improve their policies and practices to become more inclusive and benefit from the diversification of their workforce. Ultimately, BIP is set up to improve the underrepresentation of Black people in health data science.</p>			
7	5	6	3	4
Inputs	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Impact
Process			Impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + HDR UK capacity building team + BIP programme staff + Advisory group / board + Programme funding (HDR UK funding, AWS sponsorship for awards ceremony etc.) + Senior leadership buy-in (both from HDR UK and host organisations) + Communications / marketing collateral + Application and recruitment material + Application reviewers + Time/workload for sifting, communications, recruiting host organisations etc + Technological infrastructure (e.g. Box, Applied, Monday.com etc.) + Past intern volunteers + Host organisations as employers + Staff and time in host organisations to onboard, train and manage interns 	<p>BIP marketing & comms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Drafting the offer + Wide distribution + Drop-in events/promo sessions + Interns’ recruitment + Sifting and screening + Selection + Onboarding (e.g. open day) + Feedback to unsuccessful applicants <p>Host organisations’ engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Recruitment + Training and clarifying expectations + Ongoing relationship management and support <p>Internship offer content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Induction call + Intern meets + (Minimum) 8-week placement + Supervision and mentorship + Health data project + Training opportunities (some in collaboration with 10000 interns foundation and HDR Alliance) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + 308 interns gone through the programme since 2021 + Interns from a variety of backgrounds engaged + # events promoting the BIP hosted + # applications received + Applicants/acceptance ratio + # host organisations engaged + Variety of host organisations engaged and placements provided + Host organisation handbook created + Interns’ recruitment pack created + Documentation of processes and procedures outlining how BIP runs and standardised forms/ templates created + Internship offer delivered (e.g. # posters produced, interns introduced to variety of speakers etc) + Publications about the BIP programme from interns, BIP staff and other sources 	<p>Interns</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Improved data skills + Increased knowledge and understanding of health data science sector + High-quality field experience through their internship gained + Increased self-confidence + Improved, meaningful insights into career opportunities in health data science + Heightened growth mindset + Increased perceptions of being ‘job ready’ compared to before BIP engagement + Pursue aspirations to continue their careers/ education in health data science either in UK or abroad + Alumni secure jobs/ continue their education in health data science sector (including in HDR UK) + Sustained engagement with BIP post internship (advocates/ champions of the programme, alumni group activity etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Increased awareness of BIP across time amongst each target populations, which leads to increased interest in, and value attached to the programme + Increased awareness of racial inequities and biases within and beyond the health data science sector + HDR UK established as a thought leader in advancing the careers of under-represented groups in health data science + HDR UK’s established reputation as producing and sharing good practice around inclusive recruitment and developing support practices for the health data science sector + BIP and its findings inspire similar provisions from other sectoral organisations (e.g. LIDA) + Improved approach of health data science organisations regarding recruitment and support of Black people

Figure 2 / BIP Theory of Change Framework (continued)

7 Inputs	5 Activities	6 Outputs	3 Outcomes	4 Impact
Process			Impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Budget for interns' pay and expenses (currently both are host-organisation funded) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Site visits and meetings + Opening/closing ceremony + Friday guest speakers Futures playlist + Technical challenge + Poster challenge + (Feedback) surveys distribution to interns and host organisations General administration by HDR BIP staff + Managing relations & support with all stakeholders + Ongoing comms to interns (signposting to additional opportunities through newsletters etc) + Alumni community management + Advisory group meetings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Alumni network established and sustained + Datasets (from application to post-internship destinations) created for interns + Repository for host organisations created (e.g. name, place, # interns taken across time etc) + Feedback received from interns & host organisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Follow-on networks and collaborations between alumni and/or host organisations Host organisations/partners + Increased awareness of the value of diverse staff + Perceive BIP alumni as job ready + Draw from the BIP alumni pool for further employment opportunities + Sustained engagement with BIP + Improved recruitment policies and practices to attract minoritised candidates + Improved support systems in place for minoritised staff HDR UK + More inclusive organisational recruitment process + Increased organisation-wide involvement in the programme + Increased organisation-wide awareness of Black people's underrepresentation in the health data science sector + Increased understanding of how to best support Black interns (using feedback to improve BIP offer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + BIP alumni have accelerated career advancement (e.g. attain senior roles)
<p style="text-align: center;">Rationale & Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Target audiences engage with the offer in its entirety + BIP offer is relevant/useful to target audiences + Target audiences engage with and learn from the findings of the BIP programme + Interns use the skills they learnt during their internship in future practice + Host organisations and the wider sector utilise the pool of 'job ready' BIP interns to recruit from + Developments in the wider health data science ecosystem continue to be a priority for UK and international policy and investment 			<p style="text-align: center;">Rationale</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Internship programmes are known to be effective ways for improving the representation of ethnically minoritised groups (e.g. Diversity in Tech 2024; Dockry et al. 2022; Medina-Perez 2019) + Most internships are unpaid, which creates extra barriers for minoritised groups' access and participation, whose inequities are intersectional, exacerbated by lower socio-economic status (e.g. Hunt 2020; Moxon et al 2023) 	

2.3 / Stakeholder consultation

The consultation consisted of three strands, including:

- + Surveying BIP alumni and host organisation staff
- + Three focus groups with BIP alumni
- + 11 interviews with key stakeholders including HDR UK employees involved in the BIP, the programme's Advisory Group, host organisation staff as well as people from organisations familiar with the programme who have a high-level perspective of the health data science sector and EDI initiatives within it

2.3.1 / Online surveys

2.3.1.1 / BIP alumni survey

An online survey was launched on 18 November and stayed open until 23 December 2024. An invitation to complete it was distributed via direct email to all past interns for whom the HDR UK BIP team held a valid address. 111 responses were received, which represents 36% of the total BIP interns across time (n=308). A section describing the survey sample is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.2).

2.3.1.2 / Host organisation staff survey

The host organisation staff survey also launched on 18 November and stayed open until 23 December 2024. An invitation to complete it was distributed via direct email to all host organisation staff members who are listed as key points of contact and for whom the HDR UK BIP team held a valid email address. 29 responses were received, which represents 53% of the total host organisation staff contacted (n=55). A section describing the survey sample is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.3).

2.3.2 / Online focus groups

Three focus groups with BIP alumni were conducted to gain a clearer understanding of their career pathways, how the BIP contributed to their decision-making, and ways in which the programme may be improved. Independently facilitated focus groups provide an environment that enable participants to discuss their experiences and develop a 'safe space' for individuals to express themselves in a collective and supportive environment. Sessions were conducted online to maximise attendance.

BIP alumni were called to express their interest in participating in the online focus group sessions in two ways:

- + Through responding to a relevant question in the alumni online survey, following a link that redirected them in a separate system to log their contact details
- + Through an open call for participants, circulated to all relevant staff and students

Participation was reimbursed with a £10 retail voucher. The call for focus group participation remained open between 18 November and 23 December 2024. In total, 64 alumni expressed an interest in participating. From those, based on their availability, the capped capacity that we had for each session (up to eight participants per session), and their background characteristics, 34 were invited in total.

All participants received a designated session invite and two reminders. 17 participants engaged across the three sessions (50% drop-out rate). A further description of the online focus group sample is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.4).

Each focus group session lasted 90 minutes and was co-facilitated by an Advance HE researcher and an Advance HE research associate. All participants were provided with a participant information sheet and consent form as well as a draft of the discussion guide in advance of their allocated session, so that they were aware of how their data would be used, managed and stored. All sessions were conducted via Microsoft Teams and were recorded to allow for transcription and subsequent data analysis.

2.3.3 / Online interviews

The aim of conducting online interviews was to gain a more in-depth understanding of a variety of key stakeholders' perceptions regarding BIP's added value, based on their high-level perspective of the health data science sector and EDI initiatives within it.

A list of suitable participants was crafted by the BIP commissioning team. The Advance HE researchers had asked the BIP team to identify around 20 potential interview candidates, separated into relevant groups of stakeholders and ranking candidates within each group based on who they would like the Advance HE team to contact first. The BIP team was also asked

to identify how many interviewees they would like to ringfence from each category, based on the target number of 10 interviews to be conducted.

A list with 19 potential candidates, divided across the following four groups, was provided by the BIP team in late November 2024:

- + HDR UK internal members
- + HDR UK BIP advisory group members
- + BIP host organisation members
- + Health data science sector experts

Advance HE researchers and the BIP team mutually agreed for the BIP team to contact the first two potential candidates from each group, giving them some advance notice that Advance HE researchers will invite them to participate in the BIP review. Advance HE researchers would then contact the same participants after one week, inviting them to express their interest in participating in an online interview at a date and time of mutual availability until the end of January 2025.

All potential candidates were contacted through the staged approach described above by the end of December 2024. Participants had the option to receive a £10 retail voucher as a reimbursement for their time. 11 one-to-one online interviews were conducted between December 2024 and January 2025 with a variety of key stakeholders, spanning HDR UK employees involved in the BIP, the programme's advisory group, host organisation staff as well as people from organisations familiar with the programme who have a high-level perspective of the health data science sector and EDI initiatives within it. A table outlining the breakdown of interview participants across the above categories is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.5). All participants were provided with a participant information sheet and consent form as well as a draft of the discussion guide in advance of their interview, so that they were aware of how their data would be used, managed and stored. Interviews lasted between 30 minutes and one hour each, were conducted via Microsoft Teams and recorded, to allow for transcription and subsequent analysis.

3

Desk-based review findings

3.1 / Introduction and contextualisation

The BIP stands out for its strong commitment to improving the under-representation of Black health data scientists. The internship programme aims to assist Black health data scientists to gain hands-on experience, combined with structured training and mentorship. In assessing the programme's impact to date, it is valuable to compare it with other relevant initiatives to highlight similarities, differences, and possible future directions.

To achieve this, a desk-based comparative review was undertaken, based on publicly available information. Following an initial online search for comparative initiatives and discussions with the HDR UK BIP project team, three programmes were selected for this comparative review, due to their comparability in terms of the sector of focus, the under-represented groups they target, or both:

1. The [10,000 Black Interns Programme](#)
2. The [Data Scientist Development Programme](#) at the University of Leeds' Institute for Data Analytics
3. The [University of California Irvine's Public Health Informatics and Technology \(PHIT\) Internship Programme](#)

Throughout this section, each of these programmes is outlined in turn. A table provided in the Appendix (see section 7.6) provides additional information drawn from a summative overview of other relevant comparative programmes identified.

3.1.1 / The 10,000 Black Interns programme

The 10,000 Black Interns programme, launched in 2020 by the 10,000 Interns Foundation, began as a pilot initiative—100 Black Interns—aimed at tackling the under-representation of Black talent in investment management. Whilst HDR UK partners with the programme, it offers a distinct and separate service. The programme originally had roots in the field of Finance, later expanding to other sectors. Since 2021, the pledge grew, and the initiative was rebranded to its current name. Four years after its inception, the programme has turned into a registered charity working with organisations across more than 35 sectors to provide insight into industry for Black students and recent graduates (up to three years post-graduation).

This initiative provides support to participants through a structured training programme, which includes mentoring, pre-application guidance, pre-interview coaching and pre-internship preparation. An overview of the programme structure is detailed in Figure 3.

Figure 3 / 10,000 Black Interns programme structure

The 10,000 Black Interns programme offers employers access to a broad pool of talented Black students and graduates, tailored intern matching, support for inclusive onboarding and mentorship, and a pipeline for future hires—all whilst advancing workplace diversity and enhancing the organisation’s reputation. Examples of partner organisations include the NHS, Sodexo, and Amey.

As a registered charity, the 10,000 Interns Foundation depends on the support of participating organisations, charitable donors, and strategic partners. According to its 2024 impact report, the programme has created 7,000 paid internships—some of which were delivered through BIP—partnered with over 1,000 organisations and reached across a wide range of sectors.

10,000 Black Interns programme – key facts and figures

- + 50,000 young people have applied to the programme in the last four years
- + 7,000 alumni
- + Over 70% of programme alumni are currently employed, with 30% of alumni retained at their internship host organisation
- + Engaged with 1,300+ participating organisations
- + Engaged with 149 universities through campus Careers Services, and campus student societies including African Caribbean Societies
- + Corporate membership makes up 77% of the programme’s annual fundraising target
- + Offers bespoke candidate slates for Premier Members and an “early application window”
- + 10,000 applicants are tracked through the applicant tracking software [Pinpoint](#)
- + Provides employers with access to high-quality Black talent, support for inclusive onboarding, and a pathway to future hires

3.1.2 / Data Scientist Development Programme, Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA), University of Leeds

The Data Scientist Development Programme (DSDP) is a structured initiative aimed at equipping individuals, particularly those in the early stages of their careers or academic pursuits, with the necessary skills and experience for success in the field of data science. It offers a limited number of targeted placements for Black individuals, rather than a full programme dedicated exclusively to them.

The projects that participants engage with during the programme typically integrate theoretical training with practical applications, covering fundamental areas such as programming, data analysis, machine learning and big data technologies. Participants engage in hands-on projects or industry placements, receive mentorship from experienced professionals, and benefit from career development support.

The DSDP is open to graduates (Bachelor’s, Master’s, or PhD) in relevant fields such as quantitative social science, computing, mathematics, statistics, medical bioinformatics, or population studies. Participants undertake the delivery of two consecutive six-month projects, including but not limited to health data, collaborating with external partners from various sectors, including public, private, charitable and educational organisations. Career changers with appropriate skills are also encouraged to apply. The programme duration typically ranges from a few months to one year and, on completion, participants may receive certifications or academic credits.

In terms of funding, the programme benefits from both external and internal sources. With regards to external support, organisations from the public, private and third sectors collaborate with LIDA by proposing research projects and providing the necessary funding. Partners include the British Heart Foundation, the Department of Health and Social Care, The Leeds Teaching Hospital Trust, and the Office for National Statistics (ONS).

These partners benefit from dedicated data scientists working on their specific challenges, co-produced research briefs, and regular project updates. When looking at internal support, the Leeds Social Sciences Institute (LSSI) funds one DSDP position, offering social science students and career changers the opportunity to work on projects that address urgent social challenges in collaboration with academic teams and external organisations.

The programme incorporates Positive Action Recruitment by reserving positions for individuals from under-represented groups, including Black and minority ethnic candidates, women and those from low socio-economic backgrounds.

Data Scientist Development Programme – key facts and figures

- + Offers a limited number of targeted placements for Black individuals
- + Provides on-the-job training and experience in the form of a fixed 12-month, paid role. Participants own the delivery of two 6-month projects
- + Since 2016, it has provided 61 paid programme participants with hands-on experience. In recent years, several BIP Alumni have secured DSDP places
- + Won an award in 2022 for contribution in equity, diversity and inclusion
- + Partners with public, private and third sector organisations

3.1.3 / University of California – Public Health Informatics and Technology Workforce Development Programme (PHIT) – UCI PHIT Internship Programme

The Public Health Informatics and Technology Workforce Development Programme (PHIT) is funded by a grant from the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services for nearly \$7 million. The UCI PHIT

Programme offers training in health informatics and technology through various pathways, including a Health Informatics Minor for undergraduates, a paid internship program for real-world experience, a Graduate Certificate for UCI students to expand their studies, and a Healthcare and Public Health Analytics Program through Continuing Education for professionals looking to advance in healthcare and data analytics.

UCI PHIT Internship Programme

Under the umbrella of the PHIT, the first UCI PHIT Internship Programme was launched in 2022, providing UCI undergraduate and graduate students with practical experience in public health informatics. The application process involves three steps: submitting the application, applying to partner sites if selected, and finalising a placement.

The programme focuses on equipping participants with the necessary skills in health analytics to support the modernisation of healthcare systems, reduce health inequities and monitor emerging health threats. Drawing on past cycles, interns are expected to gain hands-on experience by participating in research, projects, and other relevant tasks for approximately 15–20 hours per week over a 12-week period.

UCI PHIT Internship Programme

- + Offers practical experience in public health informatics to UCI undergraduate and graduate students
- + The programme intake is approximately 110 interns per year
- + The program focuses on building skills in health analytics
- + Interns typically work 15–20 hours per week over a 12-week period
- + Has nominated PHIT Ambassadors to support programme participants with their applications, provide guidance on applying and assisting in orientation

3.2 / Comparative review with HDR UK's BIP

The following table outlines how HDR UK's BIP compares against each one of the three programmes identified in the previous section. The comparison focuses on six key areas of interest, as identified through discussions with the HDR UK project team.

1. Sector
2. Target audience
3. Internship duration
4. Funding
5. Support and training offered
6. Impact and reach

As can be seen in the Table 1 below, and the information above, the BIP is unique in its offer tailored specifically for Black people in health data science. None of the comparison programmes work in this niche. It provides participants with mentorship and career development opportunities, ensuring guidance throughout their professional journey. The programme also offers hands-on experience in health data research, allowing interns to engage directly with data analysis, research methodologies and the application of health data science within the healthcare sector.

Table 1 / Comparative analysis with HDR Black Internship Programme (BIP)

	BIP	10,000 Black Interns	LIDA	UCI PHIT Internship Programme
Target audience	+ Black students and graduates, up to 2 years after graduation	+ Black students and graduates up to 3 years after graduation	+ Early-career professionals or students. Some spaces are ringfenced for individuals from under-represented groups	+ UCI undergraduate and graduate students, including those from ethnically diverse backgrounds
Sector	+ Health data science	+ Multi sector including finance, science, law, media, health	+ Data science, across multiple sectors	+ Public health and health informatics
Internship duration	+ 8 weeks	+ 6 weeks	+ A few months to a year	+ 12 weeks
Funding	+ Host organisations and HDR UK core funding	+ Host organisations, charitable funds, and partners + Corporate Membership	+ External partnerships and internal university support. Leeds Social Sciences Institute (LSSI) funds one position	+ American Rescue Plan, a legislative package to facilitate the United States' recovery from the Covid-19 pandemic
Support and training offered ¹	+ Pre-application guidance + Curated training resources and training sessions every Friday during internship + Customised learning pathway within HDR UK Futures online learning platform + Mentorship and line management + Opportunity to participate in technical challenge + Networking + Membership of HDR UK alumni network, post-programme	+ Pre-application guidance + Pre-interview coaching and pre-internship preparation + Internship project	+ Training in data science techniques and methodologies + Mentorship and guidance from professionals + On the job applications and interview preparation	+ Training in health analytics, informatics and the application of technological tools in healthcare + Mentorship from professionals in public health informatics
Impact and reach	+ Between 2021-2024, 308 interns, working with 98 host organisations	+ 7,000 internships since 2021	+ 61 interns to date	+ 110 interns per year (330 interns since 2022)

¹ Specifics of support and training offers in comparison programmes were derived from publicly available information, with somewhat limited detail. More detail was readily available for the researchers on the BIP offer, as this was provided directly by HDR UK as part of the review. Hence there may be a degree of disproportionality in the training offers presented between BIP and the 3 comparison programmes.

4

Stakeholder engagement consultation findings

This chapter outlines the findings arising from all methods of primary data collection (namely, the alumni and host organisation staff online surveys, the online focus groups with alumni, and the online interviews with key stakeholders). The findings are presented using the following thematic areas:

- + BIP's perceived main aims/objectives and its unique selling points
- + Reasons for joining/engaging with the BIP
- + Satisfaction with the BIP offer and BIP highlights
- + Perceived benefits and value added to date
- + Post-internship BIP engagement and interns' career pathways
- + Risks, challenges and barriers
- + Suggestions for improvement

4.1 / BIP's perceived main aims/objectives and its unique selling points

Interview participants were asked to identify the BIP's main aims and objectives, as well as the attributes that differentiate the programme compared to other relevant initiatives. With regards to the former, participants highlighted the following five key areas.

4.1.1 / Address under-representation of Black people in the health data science sector

Participants focused on the main aim of the BIP, highlighting that the programme seeks to create a diverse talent pipeline by providing targeted opportunities to aspiring Black health data scientists. Interviewees noted that the intervention tackles historical racial inequities and disparities in the field by trying to enrich it with diverse perspectives through the provision of relevant training, mentorship and valuable, hands-on professional experience.

4.1.2 / Bolster interns' career development and employability

Related to the first point, participants also highlighted that the BIP aims to change the sectoral landscape in the long-term by bolstering the interns' career development and employability. Participants acknowledged that, through providing Black early-career scientists with the opportunity to work on a real-world health data research project, alongside networking and training, the BIP aimed to improve the career prospects of Black early-career scientists, who historically face lower employment rates. It was highlighted that the programme enhances both technical and soft skills, whilst empowering interns through increased self-confidence. Finally, stakeholders believed that interns gained valuable awareness of opportunities within the health data science sector, including potential educational pathways, career trajectories and relevant job titles they might not otherwise encounter. Opportunities are shared both via the placement managers/mentors as well as via the alumni network.

“

What the programme's trying to achieve is the confidence in themselves for the interns, their skills and their future, and surpassing what they expect for themselves as well. It's about them being familiar with the different opportunities within the sector and the sort of transparency and job titles that they can apply to.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

4.1.3 / Community building

Participants reported that both informal (e.g. friendship relationships) and formal networks (e.g. the alumni network) create a powerful sense of belonging among interns through the cohort effect. It was noted that the BIP alumni community extends these valuable connections well beyond the internship duration, offering continued access to resources, peer support, mentoring relationships and professional development opportunities.

4.1.4 / Long-term impact and sustainability

Participants raised that the BIP comprises support for interns, which extends beyond the placement's duration – for example, through the provision of peer mentoring as well as the Amazon Web Services (AWS) mentoring scheme. They also talked about the opportunity arising through the BIP for gathering longitudinal evidence (for example, on interns' career progression) regarding the programme's impact, emphasising how this data collection would enhance understanding of ongoing benefits and support needs.

“

We are also thinking how can we [...] have longitudinal data of career progression? So [we] don't lose, don't lose touch with any of the interns and find a way of finding out what they're doing now that's a benefit for us. But also, how can we keep in touch with them and continue a light touch support mechanism for them and their networks.

Interviewee 5, HDR UK internal member

They further noted the programme's dedication to advocating for systemic changes throughout academia and across the sector, with the explicit goal of improving engagement with and support for Black people in these environments, with a particular emphasis on improving recruitment practices.

“

A big part of my job has been to go out and advocate to other institutes. I do a lot of public speaking from an HR and recruitment perspective on the Black Internship Programme, but also how organisations have to tackle, the systemic kind of issues that we have, particularly in academia and in STEM institutes around the Black community.

Interviewee 8, HDR UK internal member

4.1.5 / Host organisations' benefits

Although most participants focused on aims and objectives related to the interns and the sector, they also highlighted specific aims and objectives in relation to the host organisations that engage with the BIP. They emphasised how the programme provides organisations with access to a diverse talent pool and a meaningful way to meet their EDI objectives. They described the initiative as offering a cost-effective recruitment process that benefits employers financially.

“

They [ie host organisations] are able to broaden their talent pool through a cheap recruiting process [...]. Because, actually, if you had to go out to find these individuals, to work alongside them to build and round out your team, what would the cost be? And I think cost would have been significantly more.

Interviewee 2, BIP advisory board member

“

I think actually they just make it as easy as possible to take part, which really matters because I'd love to say that the first thing I do in the morning is think about the diversity of my workforce, but it isn't. I've got a very big inbox and all this sort of thing. And if we'd had to make something up like this from scratch, we wouldn't have done it. We just don't have the bandwidth for it. Because someone's made it their day job to make this happen and make it easy for people, it makes it so much easier for us to all take it on.

Interviewee 7, host organisation staff

Furthermore, participants pointed out that interns bring fresh ideas, perspectives and energy to the workplace, whilst serving as additional workforce capacity. Finally, participants also observed that the programme helps foster a cultural shift towards more inclusive working environments and relevant organisational procedures, noting how this transformation extends beyond the immediate internship period to create lasting institutional change.

“

A lot of these hosts are very historical organisations. I think organisational change is very expensive and very slow. Everybody knows what the barriers are, but everybody is looking for the evidence that can drive the change. And so, I think BIP is very good at framing that these are not expensive things to do, these are not costs; they are really good investments. And I think it's still about building that evidence case, about providing some sort of tractable ways forward for the hosts and in terms of things they can do and also de-risking those embracing those changes, even though they might be costly upfront, they're actually going to be very beneficial for everybody.

Interviewee 11, sector expert

Aside from identifying the programme's main aims and objectives, interviewees also pinpointed the BIP's unique selling points, highlighting the following four main areas.

4.1.6 / Targeted focus on Black individuals

The BIP's specific framing as an initiative dedicated to Black people was unanimously raised as a unique attribute. Unlike other relevant initiatives, which may broadly address minoritised groups, interviewees acknowledged that the BIP's focused approach recognises the systemic inequities Black individuals face within employment processes, including disparities in securing interviews and job offers, and aims to provide tailored support as well as open up access to opportunities within the sector.

“

There's definitely something powerful about actively defining it as a 'Black internship' and having those criteria because it's very well known that there's a disparity in the ability of people from a Black or ethnic minority background to get to interviews, to get first jobs and then to progress in their career. And I think sometimes there's a danger, be it sort of political correctness or too many priorities, to actually not label things as they are. So, I think it's definitely [...] powerful [...] to have that clear in the title of the programme because it makes it quite clear from the outset already what the internship programme is trying to do.

Interviewee 6, host organisation staff

4.1.7 / Specialisation in health data science

The second area brought up by all participants as a unique attribute of the BIP was its targeted focus on health data science. Interviewees recognised that the BIP is the only internship initiative they know addressing this relatively up-and-coming, niche field, unlike other non-sector specific data science initiatives. Moreover, the programme bridges the gap between academic theory and practical implementation, providing hands-on experience with real healthcare challenges and access to relevant datasets.

“

The programme itself is a holistic programme in a very niche field. This isn't data science, this is health data science, which is a new sector and it's quite niche. I hadn't even heard of health data before this internship and the programme.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

“

We've not really encountered any programmes that are targeting people of Black heritage, specifically in healthcare or health data science.

Interviewee 9, sector expert

This targeted approach ensures Black professionals gain relevant expertise in this growing sector, where their perspectives are particularly valuable for addressing health inequities.

4.1.8 / Holistic and structured approach through a flexible and responsive programme design

Participants noted that the BIP is unique in the sense that it is an all-encompassing offer, focused on the opportunity to work on real-world health research problems, alongside the provision of training, mentorship and peer support. This distinguishes the BIP from regular internship programmes, which are restricted to work placements. The BIP offer is tailored to the interns' needs, benefits from sectoral insights, and is responsive to feedback from and/or changes in the aforementioned areas, another element which makes it stand out from rigid, pre-set approaches.

The fact that there's so few educational pathways to health data science means you end up training for something similar, but not the same as it. Which means, on paper, you do get to a point where on your CV you can say, yeah, I worked with a dataset and I did some coding. But when you get into the interview and they ask you about the specific data you used or the specific code you did, some of your approaches, techniques, how you overcame obstacles, [...], they want answers that are specific to health data science and that's where candidates tend to fall down. And this [...] is because it's quite hard to practise on healthcare data, because healthcare data is private [...]

So, I would say the main contributions of the BIP is getting people the real-world experience. So, they'll often be placed with an organisation that can get them access to the data. It means in that next interview, they're aware of what a health dataset looks like, they're specifically aware how messy and complicated it is, and then they can actually give answers that reflect that [...] I would also add that the advantage of HDR UK doing this is there's been five years of dedicated funding, which means [...] you get an improvement cycle each year. They learn about what worked well the previous year and what didn't. And the BIP team has been phenomenally good at actually doing that. So, it means by this year you actually have a very smooth and slick programme.

Interviewee 5, HDR UK internal member

The incorporation of feedback from multiple stakeholders – interns, host organisations, mentors and alumni – helps to refine content, structure and delivery methods. This feedback loop enables BIP to adapt to changing industry needs and incorporate lessons learnt from previous cohorts. This iterative process ensures BIP remains relevant, useful and effective in addressing both current workforce needs and the specific challenges Black professionals face in the health data science sector. Additionally, BIP provides structured post-internship support, including continued mentorship, job application assistance and alumni networking opportunities. This comprehensive follow-through distinguishes the programme from typical internships without this additional scaffolding, creating sustained pathways for Black professionals to establish themselves in the health data science sector.

“

[BIP] provides a supported end-to-end recruitment experience. Even before applicants press the 'Apply now' button, there is support for them right off the bat and there's transparency in the entire process and even unsuccessful applicants receive feedback and get signposted to other resources and relevant schemes. And this you can tell has impact because we have candidates who re-apply and become successful in later years who have come and told us that that's the case [...]

What we're trying to encourage is that health data is open to everybody, and everybody can contribute to making health data better. There's a lot of engagement in the programme, before the internship, during the internship and after the internship that actively supports the empowerment and the loyalty of our alumni as well. [...]

In terms of alumni support, there is the AWS mentorship, CPD that they can do through the workshops and the exclusive training access to them, the Futures knowledge [...] [T]here is a mentality of continuous improvement of the programme as well with each iteration.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

The training and support offered balances organisation-specific opportunities with collaborative learning experiences, simultaneously developing interns' personal skills, whilst fostering teamwork and networking.

“

The fact that you're now engaging with other students, so now you're developing additional skills, networking skills, collaborative skills, and in the end, you do a project which, you know, they then present at the closing ceremony, I think that's really value added. That's very different, I think from a standard internship programme. And that I think is powerful because what they're also doing is they're also then developing presentation skills.

Interviewee 4, BIP advisory board member

4.1.9 / Cross-country reach and engagement with variety of host organisations

The BIP delivers nationwide impact across the UK, engaging both returning and new host organisations each year to expand its reach. Participants noted that the programme partners with diverse institutions providing interns with exposure to varied health data science applications. By offering internships across various settings throughout the UK, the BIP ensures Black professionals gain experience in multiple facets of the field, whilst building connections throughout the UK's health data science ecosystem.

“

The BIP is a national programme, so all four nations are involved in it as host organisations and applicants and interns. And this reflects very much the mission of HDR UK to be a national health data institute. We have engagement and collaboration with so many different types of host organisations and sectors in health data. So, it's not just 'oh okay, this internship is in industry', 'this internship is within universities'. It's much more interdisciplinary than that. So, we work with medical research charities, both large and very small niche ones, as well NHS, both bodies and individual trusts, and civil service departments. And this year we're working with local government departmental local councils, we've got academia, in university departments or collaborations, like the NIHR, but also individual research institutes, like the Alan Turing, and then of course we've got businesses and industry partners.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

4.2 / Reasons for joining/engaging with the BIP

Alumni and host organisation staff were asked in the online surveys, as well as in the focus groups and interviews, why they chose to engage with the BIP. Specifically, alumni survey participants were provided with 11 reasons to rate in terms of their significance in prompting them to engage with the BIP, using a Likert type scale, in which 1=Not important at all and 5=Very important. Figure 4 on the following page presents these 11 reasons in a ranked order, based on their average rating.

All 11 reasons proved to be important for alumni to engage with the programme, with all receiving an average rating exceeding 4 out of 5. Getting an insiders’ perspective of what working in health data science looks like featured at the top of this list, with improving one’s CV and data skills following closely (average score: 4.7 out of 5 each). Lower down the list were items related to hearing and learning from the

experiences of Black people with an existing career in health data science and getting a mentor (average score: 4.3 out of 5 each).

These findings were corroborated during the focus group discussions. When alumni were asked what prompted them to engage with a programme, the following themes arose.

1. Practical experience to aid career advancement

The BIP offers aspiring Black health data scientists practical benefits through placements with reputable UK organisations. Participants work directly with real-world health datasets, applying academic knowledge to practical challenges. This unique experience significantly enhances interns’ CVs, leading to improved employment prospects and higher earning potential. Through hands-on experience with UK-specific workplace cultures and health data systems, interns develop technical expertise alongside the professional networks necessary for successful career advancement.

Figure 4 / Alumni – reasons for engaging with the BIP (average rating in ranked order)

2. Skills development

Furthermore, BIP participants develop industry-specific technical expertise in programming, coding and data analysis, gaining proficiency with essential tools such as Python and R. Beyond technical capabilities, interns cultivate crucial workplace competencies in project management, presentation delivery, organisational efficiency, team collaboration and effective communication – a comprehensive skillset that significantly enhances employability across academic and commercial health data science environments.

3. Networking and mentorship

Lastly, BIP offers valuable networking opportunities with experienced professionals in health data science, creating connections that frequently lead to job

offers and career advancement. Equally important, the programme fosters a community among Black data scientists who share similar backgrounds and experiences, creating a supportive environment for discussing unique challenges and opportunities. This peer network also continues beyond the programme lifespan, providing ongoing alumni support.

Similarly, host organisation staff were provided with 12 reasons to rate in terms of their significance in prompting organisations to engage with the BIP, using a Likert-type scale, in which 1=Not important at all and 5=Very important, alongside an extra option allowing them to indicate aspects that were not relevant to them. Figure 5 on the following page presents these reasons in a ranked order, based on their average rating.

Figure 5 / Host organisation staff – reasons for engaging with the BIP (average rating in ranked order)

It is clear that, for most organisations, tackling the under-representation of Black people in health data science was the main motivator for engaging with the BIP. Similarly highly-ranked was the need to improve the inclusivity of the organisations’ research culture, followed by the opportunity to get an increased understanding of the unique contributions Black people can offer in health data science. All in all, intrinsic motivations related to the need to tackle the current inequities noted in terms of the participation of Black people in health data science are the main drivers that lead host organisations to want to engage with the BIP. On the other side, more “opportunistic” motives, such as improving the organisational reputation, benefitting from partaking in the UK Health Data Research Alliance or receiving a good recommendation about the programme were perceived as least attractive.

4.3 / Satisfaction with the BIP offer and BIP highlights

Both alumni and host organisation staff were highly satisfied with the wider BIP offer and its main individual aspects. The specific highlights of the programme each group identified pointed towards similar areas.

4.3.1 / Overall satisfaction with the offer

Alumni were specifically asked to rate the recruitment and onboarding process for the BIP. Their high satisfaction was evident, as they rated each one of the six aspects provided to them with an average of 4.7 out of 5 and above (where 1=Poor and 5=Excellent, also with an option to indicate that an aspect was not applicable to them). Specifically, the opening and closing ceremonies were the aspects most highly rated (both 4.8 out of 5), with the application process, the induction call with HDR UK, the intern meet and greet, and the open day session following, with an average rating of 4.7 out of 5 each. 2023 and 2024 participants rated the opening and closing ceremonies significantly higher than their peers from 2021 and 2022, which is probably related to the fact that both ceremonies were conducted online due to Covid for the first two cohorts of the programme. These positive findings indicate that these recruitment and onboarding processes are working well and are well-received.

Figure 6 / Onboarding process aspects’ average ratings

Moreover, some alumni who chose to leave free-text comments related to their onboarding experience described the process as ‘seamless’, with the support provided at every stage from application to placement being ‘outstanding’. Praise was also given to the BIP team, with the only critical comments relating to individual requests, such as to better match interns with their places of residence, supporting organisations with how to more quickly navigate the background checks for non-UK citizens, and clearer guidance in terms of the reasonable adjustments disabled people can request whilst participating in the internship.

Recruitment and onboarding were briefly touched on by host organisation staff as well as HDR UK team members in some of their open-ended survey responses as well as some of the interviews. Overall, these processes were well-perceived, with respondents recognising their structured nature and the tremendous effort put in by the BIP team to make them run as smoothly as possible. Some challenges were also mentioned (see also section 4.7.7). These were mostly related to the following.

- + Some inconsistencies noted in the screening and selection processes across host organisations, which led to some mismatches between candidates and projects, particularly during the initial cohorts
- + The increasing use of AI in BIP applications and the subsequent heightened need for consideration of additional mitigating measures (for example, inclusion of technical tests) to ensure that the selected applicants fulfil the relevant post requirements
- + Misalignments between the BIP’s and some host organisations’ recruitment timelines, with BIP requiring processes to move faster than would be usual for host organisational procedures

The clearly positive perceptions regarding BIP recruitment and onboarding processes were retained when it came to rating the internship experience overall as well as individual elements of the offer. Specifically, alumni rated their overall BIP experience with an overwhelming 4.7 out of 5 (where 1=Poor and 5=Excellent), and each individual element provided above 4 out of 5, as visualised by the graph below.

Figure 7 / Alumni – BIP offer aspects’ average rating (ranked order)

The induction call got the highest rating, whereas the WhatsApp group, the only element not managed by the BIP team, but by the interns themselves, got the lowest (4.1 out of 5). The internship project gets very high ratings, as do the Friday guest speaker sessions and the poster challenge, despite the fact that the latter has only been offered for the last two programme cohorts.

The technical challenge average ratings present no statistically significant difference across the various cohorts, despite improvements made across the years. Open-ended responses as well as participants' comments during the focus group discussions made it clear that the technical challenge was an experience which participants who were in successful teams found extremely rewarding, whereas for others, time management and differences in team dynamics (arising by either perceived differences in the effort put in by each team member or differences in the skillsets available across different teams) made this element more challenging (see also section 4.7.3). The technical challenge is organised as such to emulate what happens in the workplace, where team dynamics and conflicting priorities have to be managed. Overall, the technical challenge was perceived as an activity that helps interns practice their team-working and leadership skills, despite any challenges arising from the team-nature of the activity.

During the focus group discussions, a dedicated question asking alumni to identify what they found most useful from the BIP clarified alumni's high satisfaction with the offer. Firstly, alumni talked about the BIP's holistic structure, as an offer which exceeds the simple placement of interns in a host organisation, by providing structured training, mentorship and support that extends beyond the end of the placement. Moreover, participants talked about HDR UK's role as a key agent, connecting interns who are unfamiliar with the job market to reputable organisations to offer them practical experience, providing them with a unique opportunity to get an insider's perspective. This was particularly mentioned by international interns, who thought BIP was a unique programme as it provided a level playing field for them, enabling them to get access to and better understand the UK health data science job market.

“

The internship gave me the opportunity to get the job I had after the internship. The internship had an alumni group, and I came across a vacancy for the job I ended up getting after the internship. The skills from the internship and that job enabled me to [subsequently] apply for a PhD programme.

FG Participant 18, 2023 intern

In the focus groups, alumni also raised the internship project as a useful aspect of the programme, corroborating the high rating this received in the survey. Alumni highlighted their appreciation of working on significant health-related projects, providing them with the opportunity to apply their skills to tackle real-world problems. Examples of projects that alumni worked on during their BIP placements include addressing NHS waiting times, improving cancer patient journeys and using the UK Biobank to look at cardiovascular disease life outcomes for people with certain comorbidities.

Alumni also mentioned how much they valued the support they got from their host supervisor/manager as well as the rest of their colleagues. Support came in many forms, ranging from regular meetings to solve issues arising whilst working on their projects, to career advice, CV and thesis reviews, as well as job applications or interview guidance.

“

I was part of a big research group. So, in that research group, there were clinicians, data scientists, software engineers who've done great things [...]. So, it was really nice to just sit with 'big fish' [...] in the data science world and [...] looking at how they handle problems, real world, clinical problems, was something that I really adored, you know, just sitting in. [...] We used to have Friday meetings for the whole research group but my supervisor, my mentor and I had Tuesday meetings [as well]. [During these meetings], whatever programming language I was using, [...] we would debug all the errors that I had, which was very, very important because if you're programming, you know how much that can get to your neck. [...] My mentor is still my mentor [...]. We have usual catch ups [...] I still walk into that office as if I work there, because she's there and the research team is still there. We talk a lot. Because I was doing my Master's then, she's the one who's been my referee to do my PhD.

FG Participant 12, 2022 intern

Mentions of the technical challenge, the poster presentation and the Friday guest speakers' sessions were also mentioned amongst the most useful elements of the BIP in the focus group discussions. The technical challenge was highlighted as a unique opportunity to allow alumni to practise their leadership and team-working skills, and the poster presentation for developing communication skills and conveying complex information in a succinct way. Some alumni mentioned using the work they have done on their presentation for subsequent job or PhD interviews, to illustrate the type of projects they have delivered.

“

While I was still doing my [BIP] internship, an opportunity was shared about a data science development programme at the University of Leeds at that time. So, I applied, I was invited for interview, and they asked me to do a presentation. I pulled together all the research and projects I was working on as part of my internship and used that to make a presentation for that job. [...] I was offered the job the next day or right then, and I am still in the same company, [although I have progressed] in a research software engineer [role].

FG participant 7, 2021 intern

Alumni explained that both the technical challenge and poster presentation contributed to them developing a 'can-do' attitude, building confidence in their abilities to solve complex issues and find resources independently. Lastly, the Friday guest speaker sessions were examples of spaces that allowed alumni to get to know aspirational role models that were relevant to them. Alumni mentioned that exposure to successful Black professionals during those sessions inspired them and reinforced their commitment to excelling in health data science careers.

Host organisation survey respondents were asked to rate the BIP offer for host organisations through rating a series of statements, using a Likert scale, where 1=Poor and 5=Excellent, with an extra option to indicate if the statement was not applicable to host organisation staff. Figure 8 below outlines participants’ responses per item in a ranked order.

Overall, host organisation staff were highly satisfied with the offer (average rating: 4.4 out of 5).

Similarly, they rate highly the communication they have with and support they receive from HDR UK throughout the BIP, with the host organisation handbook being recognised as a valuable resource. The recruitment process and timeline ratings were lower. Interview data and open-ended survey comments suggest this may be due to recruitment windows and processes running at different paces and cycles, making it hard to adhere to the BIP timeline.

The lowest rating in this list is opportunities for host organisation staff to contribute to the BIP programme delivery. However, this was also the option most respondents highlighted as ‘not applicable’ to them (17%). The low rating of this item might be because not all host organisation staff receive invites to participate in the BIP delivery.

Lastly, participants’ open-ended comments highlighted an additional stressor, centred around the increasing financial commitments for host organisations. Specifically, covering the expenses for interns’ attendance of the opening and closing ceremony was an area of concern for some respondents, who raised this as an additional ‘onus’ placed on host organisations, which initially used to be covered by HDR UK.

This area will be discussed further in sections 4.6.1 and 4.7.9, when findings around identified risks, challenges and barriers with suggestions for improvement will be explored.

Figure 8 / Onboarding process aspects’ average ratings

4.3.2 / Host organisation staff satisfaction with BIP interns

Host organisation staff were highly satisfied with their BIP interns. That was evident through the high average score given (4.4 out of 5, where 1=Poor and 5=Excellent), as well as through high ratings for other relevant items included in the survey. Figure 9 on the following page outlines the relevant items' average rating in a ranked order, rated using a 5-point Likert scale, where 1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree.

Host organisation staff indicate that BIP interns met their expectations, although they did not necessarily exceed those. Some host organisation staff mentioned that they did not rate this item as highly, as they already had high expectations of their interns, or because they had mixed experiences from the various interns they hosted over the years, with some being outstanding, most meeting expectations and a few not meeting their standards.

Host organisation staff believe that BIP interns are better equipped to pursue careers and/or studies in health data science after their internship completion. There was also consensus that hosts would highly recommend BIP interns to other health data science organisations, if they were recruiting. Finally, respondents mostly agreed that their organisation would hire a BIP intern for a full-time paid role (3.9 out of 5). Interview data and survey open-ended responses indicate that a reason for the slightly lower rating on the latter item may be because some organisations have specific recruitment or job requirements, which their intern did not fit (e.g. MSc qualification, nationality/continuous residency status etc). This might also explain the relatively low percentage of respondents who indicated their organisation had hired some of their previous interns (17%). Some organisations reported recruiting former BIP interns who did not intern with them, and that BIP alumni often make their shortlisting and interview stage. Also, where interns did not meet essential recruitment criteria, organisations mentioned internship contract extensions as an alternative, which should be used as testament for the host organisations' appreciation of the interns' work and value.

Figure 9 / Host organisation staff average ratings in items related to their satisfaction with BIP interns

4.3.3 / BIP highlights

Both alumni and host organisation staff members were asked to identify the highlights of the BIP through a free-text survey question. Answers were thematically analysed.

From alumni responses, the following five key areas were highlighted.

1. Technical skills development

Participants mentioned significantly improving their technical skills through the hands-on experiences they got via their internship projects as well as the technical challenge. Specifically, participants mentioned enhancing their coding abilities, learning to use specific packages, such as R and Python, and practical experiences in data analysis and visualisation.

Using machine learning to analyse experimental data. It gave a grasp of what the day of a data scientist looks like and how to implement current technologies.

Alumni survey respondent 9, 2023 intern

2. Networking

The various opportunities that the BIP offered to participants to build professional networks with health data science experts, as well as mentors and peers, was another highlight. Attending the opening and closing ceremonies, training events and the mentorship opportunities provided during the internship were key examples of opportunities for networking.

Having the opportunity to work and network with academics and a brilliant cohort of interns with whom I wouldn't have ever interacted on my own. This provided me with insight into the health data landscape and how to prepare for a future job in health data science after the programme.

Alumni survey respondent 6, 2022 intern

Findings from the focus group discussions highlight the importance of networking even further. Alumni mentioned how attendance at high-profile events, ranging from specialist Society events to conferences and House of Lords receptions, helped them to establish connections with policymakers, clinicians and other key stakeholders, which resulted in further professional opportunities, such as committee roles, or even employment posts. The following quotes illustrate some indicative examples.

We were invited to the House of Lords to [...] a reception [with] leaders, lawyers, policymakers, [...] to sit down and think about the health landscape of the country [...]. From there I got lots of connection with one of the policymakers in health science and [...] he connected me to a project in Africa [...] and in that team, you know, I'm making lots of impact, which is good. I wouldn't have got this experience without this internship, and we were also invited [...] to the first Black in Cancer conference which was held in the UK.

FG participant 1, 2022 intern

The BIP put me [in] contact with some people I didn't have contact with while I was studying. I presented my research in a conference and then through the internship I was able to meet people in the field I was interested in the NHS Cancer Inequality team. So, I was able to get in contact with the national team who I'm now currently working with as a Core20PLUS ambassador.

FG participant 4, 2024 intern

3. Collaborative work arising through internship projects and the technical challenge

Group project work was a significant highlight, fostering the interns' teamwork and problem-solving skills. Examples mentioned under this theme include: a) participants' experiences of and/or winning the technical challenge, b) engagement in collaborative projects that were valuable to host organisations and relevant to team objectives, c) working on impactful, real-world projects, allowing interns to put their skills into practice.

The culture [in my host organisation] was immensely remarkable. I had the opportunity to work beyond being a data scientist intern, to integrating clinical knowledge in data science, which was lacking at the time. I had the chance to work for three different teams and on different projects. Although I had a direct line manager, it felt like I had over four managers because of the overwhelming support I got. That goes beyond the internship. My host organisation set the foundation for my current role.

Alumni survey respondent 8, 2023 intern

4. Personal growth, confidence and aspiration building

Participants mentioned the educational and/or career pathways they followed after their participation in the programme, as well as increased confidence and self-growth. Continued studies, further job roles and/or extensions of their internship placements were mentioned here, as well as increased self-confidence in their skills and abilities to aim higher and achieve a career in health data science or other relevant fields.

The programme pushed me out of my comfort zone, helping me build confidence in my abilities and inspiring me to aim higher in my career.

Alumni survey respondent 7, 2022 intern

5. Supportive environments

Participants highly appreciated the supportive and inclusive environments provided by both the BIP team as well as their host organisations. Support received from managers and supervisors, as well as relationships developed with fellow interns, were some of the examples that featured under this theme.

[My host organisation] inspired my goals to study a Master's degree in Health Data Science. It was great to finally meet the team, be part of working with health data research and being given the opportunity to work in a host organisation. The host organisation furthered my networks, supported me throughout the internship and extended my internship after the BIP one ended.

Alumni survey respondent 27, 2022 intern

Alumni also rated highly their relationship with their internship supervisor/manager (average score: 4.7 out of 5), with 66.7% of the survey respondents indicating that they have stayed in touch with them even after the end of their internship. This shows that an important relationship has developed, which lasts over time and is valuable for the interns. Most of those participants indicated retaining their relationships with their supervisors/managers to benefit from ongoing mentorship and support, such as providing letters of recommendation, CV reviews and interview preparation, as well as signposting to relevant job opportunities. The following quotes further illustrate these points.

My BIP manager has been incredible, and I am grateful for the continued relationship we've maintained. We still keep in touch and have quarterly catchups where we discuss updates, my experiences, and future goals. He consistently provides valuable advice and remains a great mentor, offering guidance that has been instrumental in my professional development.

Alumni survey respondent 7, 2022 intern

“

I am deeply grateful for the incredible support and guidance provided by both [supervisor's name] and [line manager's name] throughout my internship and beyond. [Supervisor's name] has been exceptionally supportive, not only in helping me navigate the internship but also in providing invaluable career advice and serving as a referee for several job applications. Her encouragement and mentorship have significantly boosted my confidence in pursuing my career aspirations. [Line manager's name] has been equally amazing, offering consistent support and guidance as my line manager. She went above and beyond by serving as a guest lecturer in a training session on R-Instant for one of my professional groups in [country's name retracted], which added immense value to the session. Her expertise and willingness to contribute have left a lasting impression.

Alumni survey respondent 21, 2023 intern

A few individuals chose to leave a comment regarding a lack of contact with their internship supervisors/managers. This was mainly due to time lapsing, with interns hesitant to contact their supervisors/managers after a long period of no communication. There were only two cases in which participants mentioned taking an informed decision to not retain a relationship with their manager/supervisor (both from the first BIP cohort).

From the host organisation staff responses, the theme most frequently raised was having the opportunity to contribute to the development of a diverse pool of young scientists. Staff mentioned the importance of providing the interns with the opportunity to get an insider's perspective of hands-on work in the sector, and how they had benefitted from hosting the interns in terms of incorporating diverse perspectives within their teams.

“

It is great to host engaged and motivated interns and provide them with good health data science work experience that we are confident will help them to get further opportunities in health data science. We value the opportunity to host interns and address the under-representation of Black people in health data science and senior academic roles.

Host organisation survey respondent 28

Other frequently mentioned areas were watching the interns growing in confidence and skills, and listening to them talk about how much they have achieved and benefitted from their internships. Staff were excited to see all the interns had achieved throughout their experience, whether this was in internal organisational opportunities or in external events, such as the closing ceremonies.

“

It was rewarding to see the interns present their work to 300 people in our organisation and watching them converse with our Director General in a QA session. Their outputs were also very good.

Host organisation survey respondent 11

Another theme focused on the opportunities afforded to network with other interns and host organisations. The closing ceremonies were mentioned here, alongside the opening ceremonies and other activities organised as part of the internship offer (for example, hosting learning and collaboration day, career panels etc). The final two themes raised as highlights by staff in their open-ended comments were the interns' enthusiasm and energy and the opportunity that participation in the BIP provides for host organisations to provide management experience to staff who do not have such responsibilities in their current job roles.

“

It has been great to be involved in a programme which celebrates diversity in its intern cohort and in its local delivery. We have involved staff from across our organisation in the programme, and it has offered development opportunities to staff who are typically less likely to access them, e.g. line management.

Host organisation survey respondent 2

4.4 / Perceived benefits and value added to date

Perceived benefits gained from engaging with the BIP were explored at all stages of primary data collection with both alumni and host organisation staff. Similarly, a question exploring the value added to date by the programme was posed to interviewees who fell outside the above categories.

A picture of overall satisfaction arose through both alumni and host organisation survey respondents' average ratings in terms of their perceived gains from engaging with the BIP. Alumni were given 19 target areas to rate (see Figure 10).

They indicated that the programme benefited them in each one of these target areas, with time management and 'big picture' thinking getting the highest ratings (average rating: 4.6 out of 5 for both), with writing skills the least (average rating: 4 out of 5).

Figure 10 / Alumni's perceived benefits from engagement with the BIP
(1= Not benefitted at all, and 5=Benefitted a lot)

Surveyed interns also responded extremely positively when asked if they would recommend the programme to their peers, with an average scoring of 4.8 out of 5 (where 1= strongly disagree and 5 = strongly agree).

Host organisation survey respondents were asked to rate a series of nine items to indicate how much they felt their organisation had benefitted through their engagement with the BIP, using the same 5-point Likert scale as alumni. Figure 11 illustrates the average ratings for each item, in a ranked order.

Survey respondents indicated that their host organisations had more than somewhat benefitted in each one of the nine target areas. The top three rated items were related to awareness-raising around the value added by a diverse workforce, increased understanding of how to shape inclusive cultures, and increased awareness of racial inequities faced by Black people in the sector.

The areas that received lower ratings were those related to the implementation and/or diversification of specific policies, processes and procedures so that these become more inclusive and relevant to people beyond the BIP interns (such as employees or potential candidates from minoritised backgrounds). This is to be expected as awareness-raising and understanding are more easily malleable to change and the first steps towards anti-racist working cultures and practices, whilst practical implementation changes require more time, investment and senior approval to occur.

The items rated lowest by participants were having access to a ‘job-ready’ pool of diverse applicants and practically implementing more inclusive recruitment policies and procedures. The former might be related to the specificities of the recruitment policies of some host organisations; BIP interns may not have been considered ‘job-ready’, if they did not fulfil essential recruitment criteria (for example, minimum qualification of MSc degree, visa and residency status etc). The latter is a sign of the difficulties in changing recruitment practices and procedures, which might fall outside the key host organisation staff’s remit and require tailoring and senior-leadership approval. Indeed, both these justifications fit with what host organisation staff raised.

Figure 11 / Host organisation respondents’ average ratings of perceived organisational gains from BIP engagement

The general standard of interns has been high [...] We have taken eight in total now [...] We have made sure to offer the interns support in finding a new role, and a number have done so within the wider civil service (just not within our department – we're on headcount controls so haven't had many roles and the timing isn't in the interns favour with our recruitment calendar).

Host organisation survey respondent 3

Many of our interns are in the process of completing an undergrad. We do not normally employ researchers without a MSc. So, the interns are not really at the stage where we hire them for research positions. One intern had a two-month contract extension as a research assistant to complete some of the work during his internship.

Host organisation survey respondent 28

Both alumni and host organisation staff were provided with an additional free-text survey question, asking them to highlight the top three benefits from engaging with the BIP. For alumni, technical and transferrable skills development were rated most highly, with interns mentioning enhanced programming, data analysis and visualisation skills, alongside project management, communication and presentation skills. Similar themes followed to those mentioned above for programme highlights – networking opportunities, career advancement, self-confidence and personal growth. These themes were also raised by all interviewees as the top value added to date by the BIP. The following quotes summarise the positive feelings surrounding the overall BIP experience, highlighting all the different areas in which alumni felt they have benefitted:

Participating in the HDR UK BIP was a transformative experience for me. It allowed me to work on impactful projects [...]. These projects helped me sharpen my skills in NLP (natural language processing), data mapping, and structuring [...] free text into actionable data formats. The programme provided invaluable exposure to real-world applications of health data science. I gained hands-on experience translating complex datasets into insights that could support clinical decision-making, which deepened my understanding of how health informatics can make a tangible difference.

One of the biggest takeaways was the opportunity to connect with experts and peers in the field. Networking with professionals and researchers broadened my perspective and opened doors to future opportunities, including my current PhD journey. The mentorship and guidance I received during the programme helped me gain confidence in my research capabilities and prepared me to tackle the challenges of independent research. Additionally, I developed a stronger understanding of the UK health data landscape, including the importance of data governance and data standards. This knowledge has been invaluable for my academic and professional growth, particularly as I aim to contribute to health data science innovations on a global scale. The internship equally reinforced my passion for this field and played a pivotal role in shaping my career trajectory, equipping me with the skills and experiences needed to take the next steps as a health data scientist.

Alumni survey respondent 27, 2022 intern

“

The BIP internship was transformative in expanding my skill set and knowledge base. Before joining [my host organisation], I had no prior experience with SAS (Statistical Analysis System) [...]. However, through the learning opportunities provided for the role and the supportive environment, I successfully carried out impactful projects [...]. Not only did the internship enrich my technical and analytical skills, but it also gave me the confidence to tackle new challenges, ultimately leading to a permanent position at [my host organisation]. The opportunity to learn, grow and contribute meaningfully during the internship marked a pivotal step in my professional development.

Alumni survey respondent 90, 2024 intern

Host organisation staff indicated that the main benefit they felt their organisation gained through engaging with the BIP was a heightened realisation of the advantage of having a diverse workforce, and bringing in diverse perspectives in particular, alongside increasing their understanding about current inequities that Black early-career scientists face. This was also raised as the top valued added to date in host organisations by interviewees.

“

It is a tangible annual reminder of the importance of having a representative workforce in [name of sector redacted] analysis – I have to get our [BIP] participation cleared through people considerably more senior, which means I get to remind them why it matters!

Host organisation survey participant 2

“

Host organisations definitely benefit from access to very talented individuals. They can extend things, offer positions after that. I also just think it helps maybe overcome any unconscious bias in later interviews with other people. From having seen a sort of a diversity of people in the talent pool already and have worked with them closely rather than be seeing a CV for the first time and maybe make some, some assumptions about what people can and can't do.

Interviewee 3, HDR UK internal member

The second most popular answer raised in the free-text survey question and interviews related to BIP highlights for host organisation staff was gaining insights into how to make their workplace culture, particularly recruitment and onboarding processes, more inclusive. Most of the answers coded under this theme were relevant to improving processes, which could be used in future internship programmes as well as adaptations in wider recruitment and onboarding organisational practices.

“

The programme pushed us to challenge barriers to taking on people from other countries into our organisation, it was a major change working with our resourcing and security teams and setting up IT mitigation arrangements. It has shown it is possible.

Host organisation survey participant 11

Within HDR UK as an organisation, practices piloted in the BIP were applied later on across the organisation and, gradually, involvement in various aspects of the programme spread outside the core BIP delivery team.

HDR UK used the Applied platform on the first cohort of BIP to promote a blind, accessible and inclusive recruitment process. As a result of that success, HDR UK now uses this company-wide for all recruitment. We've hired five of our former interns and the programme itself I think has affected the organisation in the sense that every team in the company is involved in the programme in some way. So, either they're reviewing applications for us or they're helping us with the events, or they're taking on interns or they're involved in the technical challenge or the poster challenge. It's something that people are really proud to be associated with. They celebrate intern successes, they promote us for internal awards, etc.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

An equally popular theme raised by host organisation staff was that participation in the BIP helped teams gain experience in how to successfully onboard junior colleagues, including offering mentorship and adjusting expectations accordingly from entry-level staff.

[BIP has provided the organisation with the opportunity to] give training opportunities to our staff in areas of mentorship, recruitment and project management and in building a more inclusive workforce.

Host organisation survey participant 21

Three remaining themes from host organisation staff were, first, having the opportunity to recruit the interns as well-needed additional team members who, despite their short-term presence, were valuable in terms of delivering organisational projects and contributing their diverse perspectives. Secondly, networking, and the relationships that developed with BIP alumni and the BIP project team. Thirdly, having access to a talent pool. Some staff mentioned already having recruited BIP alumni, although not necessarily the interns they hosted. Others understood that they would tap in to this talent pool in the longer term.

When I look at recruitment, we get a really high percentage of interns applying for roles with us, which is fantastic. Some of them are successful. We also know through the alumni network that lots of them are moving into the careers that they wanted. We're seeing them going off and getting other internships or doing PhDs. I think for us, what's been really exciting is seeing the switch. So, we had a lot of interns that had come from nursing, pharmaceutical, maths, all sorts of other things, because they'd suddenly heard about this health data science thing. And we're seeing them actually moving into and starting those career journeys. So, it's exactly what we'd planned and wanted for them. That's exciting, I think. From a host organisation perspective, my sense is that we are retaining many of the organisations that started on the journey with us. We're also seeing them talking in such a positive way. When you look at the communications that they're wanting to send out and the messages that they're talking about in terms of the impact of this programme on their thinking, on their organisation, also that they're taking, you know, we've seen so many cases of people actually recruiting interns following their internship or extending internships. So that tells us that something good is happening.

Interviewee 9, HDR UK internal member

“

We have hired a former BIP intern, however they weren't someone who was hosted by us. [...] [It is also] worth noting that in the round of recruitment for the alumna we employed, the second strongest candidate was also a BIP alumna. We're currently out for advert again, and have received maybe double the expected interest... which coincides with [the opportunity] being advertised in BIP networks. I would not be surprised if we had more alumni in the current shortlist.

Host organisation survey respondent 15

An important theme raised during the interviews was the establishment of HDR UK, and the BIP in particular, as a pioneer in setting up interventions to address inequities related to access, participation and outcomes of Black scientists within the health data sector. This was manifested through the publicity (such as articles in the [Lancet Digital Health](#), [Technology Networks magazine](#), [Bloomberg](#), as well as a mention in the [Medical Research Council's strategic delivery plan 2022-25](#)), and awards that the BIP has received (for example, [2022 Corp Comms Award for best diversity and inclusion initiative](#)). Another sign of the added value of the programme is the influence of the BIP model on other similar initiatives set up within the sector (such as the [Cancer Research UK Black Leaders in Cancer PhD programme](#), [Black in Cancer mentorship programme](#), as well as ring-fencing some of the [Leeds Institute for Data Analytics at the University of Leeds – Data Science Development Programme](#) for Black and other minority ethnic participants).

“

We're sort of asked quite frequently to speak to others about similar initiatives. So, for example, Cancer Research UK and their Black leaders in cancer, Diabetes UK reached out to us. Then there's an awareness of HDR UK in sort of wider media. We were sort of published about the programme in the Lancet Digital Health and Bloomberg wrote a piece quite early on in the programme about the Applied recruitment process we used. The fact that we're recognised for awards both internally and externally as well, shows I think the value of the programme.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

Overall, host organisation staff seem to highly value their participation in the BIP and recognise the benefits that the interns and the programme bring to their organisations. This also became evident through the very high average rating respondents gave to whether they would recommend BIP participation to other organisations in the health data science sector (average rating: 4.7 out of 5).

“

The BIP is extremely well run and the interns and organisations well supported. This is what keeps us hosting the interns year after year. Also [we are] extremely impressed with the quality of candidates we work with. Taking part in the BIP has opened my eyes to the challenges Black people face in the job market. I have had better interviews from undergraduate interns than I have had from candidates applying to senior roles here. The fact that these exceptional candidates are not getting jobs equal to their talent shows the disadvantages stacked against them. I hope that we can do more to make our organisation more inclusive, to attract a wider talent pool.

Host organisation survey participant 21

4.5 / Post-internship BIP engagement and interns' career pathways

4.5.1 / Post-internship BIP engagement

BIP past interns remain engaged with the wider BIP alumni community in various ways. Out of the six options provided to survey respondents, engagement with the LinkedIn BIP alumni group was the most popular response (84% of the alumni survey respondents said they were members of the group). 45% were members of the WhatsApp BIP alumni cohort groups, 41% took part in the AWS mentoring scheme (which has been a later addition to the programme, only available for the 2023 and 2024 cohorts), 18% got involved with the BIP alumni mentoring scheme, and 19% participated in BIP's provisions for subsequent cohorts (as an invited speaker, co-host of open day session etc).

57% of alumni remained involved with the BIP post their internship ending in more than one way, suggesting additional evidence of their satisfaction with the programme, which leads them to want to stay invested in this provision. The most frequent combination of post-internship involvement was membership in both the LinkedIn and the WhatsApp alumni groups (35% of alumni survey respondents indicated this combination).

Participants were highly satisfied with all these ways of sustaining their engagement with the BIP. Involvement in subsequent cohorts got the highest rating, with the AWS mentoring scheme the second highest. Figure 13 on the following page outlines the average rating attributed to each component.

Figure 12 / Post-internship BIP engagement

Figure 13 / Post-internship BIP engagement methods' average rating (ranked order)

Involvement in subsequent cohorts was an aspect that received many mentions in the focus group discussions. Alumni highlighted that they got a lot of satisfaction from being invited to contribute to subsequent cohorts' provision, as they felt this was a way to give back to the community. Although involvement in subsequent cohorts seemed to be an option predominantly offered to alumni from the previous year, it was clear that alumni from across all cohorts would be keen to continue their involvement with the provision. Some of those had taken up the opportunity to be mentors for the alumni mentoring, whereas others were advocating for the programme either formally or informally, raising awareness about the provision and even assisting prospective candidates with how to best prepare their applications.

“

Aside from HDR UK itself, it's we, the alumni network. It's what we can do because we're already part of the programme. So, it's basically saying 'I'm HDR UK BIP alumna/alumnus'. [...] We have to be interested in helping others come in. [...] I get to sell that idea in case someone is interested. [...] I feel we, as graduates of the programme, we make ourselves available for those who are about to come into the programme, answer some questions for them, prepare them, [...] put these new applicants in place to go in there and put in proper applications.

FG participant 8, 2023 intern

Alumni mention gaining additional skills themselves out of engaging with subsequent cohorts, outside of giving back to the community. The ability to see how BIP processes work and how feedback is incorporated, and having the opportunity to get involved with evaluation and further interact with people from the advisory board, were considered to be invaluable growth experiences.

“

After I finished my internship, I was invited to serve in the advisory committee for one year. During that time, I learned a lot. [...] The experiences that I got from there, like how a programme is set up from the background until it comes to existence, it did open me up to a lot of aspects. I learned some details like writing minutes. We had the advisory board sessions monthly [...] and [...] after the meetings, we would receive the meeting minutes from the BIP programme manager. And recently, when I tried setting up my own NGO with an aim to improve vaccination coverage in Africa, I found all that the skills that I did gain from serving on that committee very useful. I use directly the meeting minutes' template, for example [...] We also did a lot of other stuff like, I was in charge of reviewing applications from subsequent cohorts and evaluating Friday session speakers and I got a great deal from there, too.

FG participant 17, 2022 intern

4.5.2 / Post-internship BIP alumni pathways

Since completing their internship, BIP interns have progressed in their educational and career pathways. Specifically:

- + 62% of the alumni survey respondents indicated having secured a job
- + 41% have continued their education
- + 7% had secured another internship

Since the BIP aims to improve the under-representation of Black scientists in health and data science, it is important to look at alumni career pathway figures in this domain in particular.

Again, these outline a picture of success, as 43% of the total alumni survey respondents indicated having continued their education and/or got a job in health data science, health technology or data science. Specifically, out of the total alumni survey respondents:

7% have done at least another internship in health data science, health technology or data science

Importantly, alumni attribute their post-internship career and educational pathways to their engagement with the programme. Survey participants agreed that participation in the BIP played a role in subsequent career choices. Figure 14 shows alumni average ratings of the extent that participation in the BIP influenced them in securing employment, another internship and/or continuing their education, using a Likert scale where 1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree for their ratings.

The biggest agreement about the BIP’s role was in terms of those participants who secured another internship (average score: 4.2 out of 5), then for those securing a job (average score: 4 out of 5), and lastly for those that continued their education (average score: 3.5 out of 5).

Amongst only those participants who took up subsequent opportunities related to health data science, health technology or data science, there are increases in the perceived contribution of their BIP participation in securing employment (average score: 4.3 out of 5) as well as in securing a PhD (average score: 4.5 out of 5).

Figure 14 / Total alumni survey respondents – perceptions of BIP’s role in subsequent career pathways

Figure 15 / Alumni who continued in health data science, health technology or data science – perceptions of BIP’s role in subsequent career pathways

In focus group discussions, alumni were also vocal about the effect of their BIP engagement on their subsequent career pathways. This has already been highlighted in some of the quotes presented previously (for example, see Section 4.4, p.43-44). Alumni describe their participation in BIP as a life-changing opportunity that opened doors and accelerated their further career development, either in terms of the type of roles they secured or even their salary.

“

[Through] the alumni group, I came across a vacancy for the job I ended up getting after the internship. And then the skills from the internship and that job enabled me to apply for the PhD programme and come out tops among multiple candidates. So, in that sense it helped with the PhD [,too]. I [also] gained lifelong mentors. I did the internship in 2023, but my supervisor is still my mentor. We still have check-in meetings every other month and that's been helpful. [...] [Finally], I've gotten the 'can do' attitude. So, nothing is too difficult, nothing is too hard to figure out.

FG participant 18, 2023 intern

“

Personally, I didn't have any other previous experience, but, where I work now, the three months [...] I spent in my BIP host organisation, accelerated the salary I have been paid. When I look at my colleagues who also didn't have experience, I am paid significantly more. So, yeah, the internship gave me the opportunity to get higher pay.

FG participant 6, 2023 intern

Additionally, alumni and host organisation staff were unanimous that having the BIP participation as an experience listed on a CV made alumni more attractive, either as PhD candidates or as potential employees. This is a sign of the programme's wider recognition across the sector.

“

Once [people] see you've been from the HDR UK [BIP], [...], people want to work with you. [...] Particularly [...] during the PhD applications I've made, at one time, I had reached out to a professor, and he read through my CV and he was like, you have a great CV. And he was very much about pointing at the HDR UK experience.

FG participant 4, 2024 intern

“

[F]or me, it helped open opportunities in organisations. When you submit your CV and somebody realises 'oh, you were able to get an opportunity with HDR UK' [...] The organisations that HDR UK have connected to help us work with, are like top-level organisations, so [having] that on your CV, it opens up a lot of opportunities, so, it's really good.

FG participant 11, 2023 intern

4.5.2.1 / Employment pathways

Out of the 69 alumni survey respondents who indicated securing a job after their BIP internship, 63% indicated that they had only secured one role, whereas the remaining indicated having secured at least two subsequent roles. Out of those who had secured multiple roles post their internship, 78% had had just one other job, 19% had had two more jobs and one participant had had three additional roles.

The 69 respondents who were employed at the time of the survey had been in their post for an average duration of 10 months (M=9.7 months, min=1 month and max=3 years and 3 months). Most of these jobs were data analyst posts (including health data analyst) (28%), data scientists (including health data scientists) (19%) and computer engineers (13%). Other roles mentioned by respondents included researcher roles, business administration roles, pharmacists and medics, and education-related roles.² The majority of survey respondents were on full-time contracts (87%).

4.5.2.2 / Education pathways

Out of those alumni respondents who continued their education, 45% did a Master's degree, 26% a PhD, 19% engaged with some other form of education (mostly online certification or training courses), and 11% did an undergraduate course.

From those BIP alumni who were pursuing an undergraduate degree, the majority (60%) were in Medicine, Dentistry and Health, and in a Russell Group university (80%). The full details of all the undergraduate degrees pursued is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.7, Table 12).

From those BIP alumni pursuing a Master's degree, 43% were studying Medicine, Dentistry and Health, and Engineering and Technology respectively, with the remaining degrees conducted in Biological, Mathematical and Physical Sciences. The most popular disciplinary area for Master's degrees was Data Science (38%), followed by Biosciences and Health Data Sciences (14% each). 57% of alumni pursuing a Master's degree were based in non-Russell Group universities. Only four alumni mentioned having secured funding to pursue their studies. The full details of all Master's degrees pursued is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.7, Table 13).

Of those alumni pursuing a PhD after the BIP, most (25% each) were in Clinical Medicine and Computer Sciences. The majority of these degrees were in Russell Group institutions (58%) and pursued with secured funding (92% of respondents indicated having secured some source of funding). The full details of all the PhD degrees pursued is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.7, Table 14).

4.5.2.3 / Securing another internship

Of those securing another internship, 100% had engaged with at least one subsequent opportunity related to health data science, health technology or data science. Participants mentioned engaging with between one and five subsequent internship opportunities, the majority of which were paid. Specifically, half had engaged with just one subsequent internship, 25% had engaged with two internships, and from the two remaining participants, one had engaged with three and the other with five subsequent internships. A table outlining the names and characteristics of these opportunities in detail is presented in the Appendix (see section 7.7, Table 15).

² A table presenting the full list of the job titles mentioned by participants is provided in the Appendix (see section 7.7, Table 11).

4.6 / Risks, challenges and barriers

4.6.1 / Resource and financial constraints

Despite agreement amongst all participants that the BIP team has delivered a high-quality programme for both interns and host organisations, interview data indicated some concerns related to the team’s staffing, should the programme grow further. Interview participants talked about challenges for the long-term sustainability of the programme due to the continuous growth in applicant numbers over time, combined with high turnover of host organisations and subsequent time spent recruiting new hosts each year. Most of the time, these concerns were centred around the size of the BIP team and the sustainability of single-person dependencies for the delivery of some aspects of the programme, if the programme expanded further.

Figures 16 and 17 below illustrate secondary analysis of programme data provided by the BIP team. Figure 16 shows growth in applicant numbers between 2021 and 2024, and number of internship placements each year. Figure 17 shows numbers of host organisations in each year, between 2021 and 2024.

Figure 16 / BIP interns – application to appointment figures, 2021-2024

“
I think that because of the dedication and commitment and talent of the people that are running the BIP, it means the programme is of high quality. However, in terms of sustainability and durability, we’ve got to think, how do we build around that? We’re doing this on a shoestring.
 Interviewee 5, HDR UK internal member

“
I think we’re doing as much as we can with the resources we have. And so, if this programme was to keep running as it is, I think the internship experience would largely stay the same.
 Interviewee 3, HDR UK internal member

Striking the right balance between resources and growth is essential for maintaining BIP’s reputation and success. This became clear though the comments of some host organisation members as well as HDR UK internal staff, who noted the increasing complexity of

Figure 17 / BIP host organisation engagement, 2021-2024

maintaining quality standards across a growing body of applicants, whilst simultaneously recruiting and managing relationships with host organisations – all with the same limited resources.

“

I think BIP should consider focusing its efforts on a smaller, promising cohort of data scientists, as opposed to delivering at greater scale as I think this has affected the quality of candidates invited to take part.

Host organisation survey respondent 2

“

[For me] it's kind of can your ambition match what you can actually deliver? Yeah, and it is really difficult because we have limited resource, limited budgets and actually so much talent. You know, when we see those numbers of interns growing year on year who want to come and do this, this, it is a real challenge, which then goes into that challenge of recruiting host organisations.

Interviewee 8, HDR UK internal member

Finally, the monitoring and evaluation activities, which staff recognised as crucial for continuous improvement, were also noted to be compromised by resource limitations.

“

The next step is capturing impact. We are limited in capturing changes in recruitment processes, changes that the internship has created within individual organisations. And then I guess the big one that everybody wants to know is that long-term destination data. So that solid tracking over time, not only is there no capacity to do this, but there's also, it's really difficult to maintain that engagement over time as well.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

Beyond internal management challenges, staff interviews revealed concerns about the financial burden being placed on host organisations. This financial pressure was identified as a potential factor contributing to host organisation attrition, with staff noting that smaller organisations with more limited resources were particularly vulnerable. This created a worrying dynamic where smaller hosts – which might offer unique and valuable placement opportunities – faced disproportionate challenges in maintaining their participation in the programme.

“

The challenge is really about getting host organisations involved [...] EDI is one of those things that goes in waves, doesn't it? [...] You know there's a case where 'wow, hold on, this is really important, we got to address this' and then it may no longer be top of the agenda, so to speak. And so, I see that as a challenge and equally there is also a financial [challenge] because BIP internships are paid and rightly so because we don't want them to be exploitative in nature. And so that means that host organisations that might be strapped for cash then combine it with maybe EDI being slightly lower down the agenda. [...] I can understand when money is tight your priorities will differ and that's natural. So that I see as a challenge and to get more host organisations involved.

Interviewee 4, advisory board member

“

Goodwill is the biggest risk – for example, the host organisations’ pledge form, that it’s not contracted. The entire programme is held together by this goodwill at every point in the process. So, health data is a sector that people join to do some good in the world. They don’t join to make money. [...] They do it because they want to make people’s experience and benefit people’s lives. So, host organisations in our programme are already people who are more likely to participate in this programme because they already understand the problems within healthcare currently, about inequality of access and lack of equity for Black people. And this is doubly true of nonprofit organisations working in health data within medical research, for example, charities.

So, this leads subsequent limitations. One, there’s a heavy reliance on these organisations to host interns yearly and these organisations are themselves susceptible to changes within the market, socioeconomic factors and political trends. So, essentially, the limitation that follows from that is that each year it becomes harder to recruit host organisations into the programme.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

Secondary analysis of programme data offers additional support to concerns related to keeping the host organisations engaged across time.

Figure 18 / Number of host organisations by years of engagement with the BIP (2021-2024)

Although the number of host organisations engaging in the programme each year is between 20 and 54, the majority of those engage with the programme for just one year and only four host organisations remained engaged across all years.

4.6.2 / Dataset accessibility and data skills

It was noted by participants that limited access to health datasets for training and project work presents a significant obstacle in terms of the variety of projects they can work on as part of their technical challenge, and also in terms of the depth they can get into with their insights into what real-world healthcare analytics look like.

In terms of limitations and challenges, there is health data training sets. So actual health datasets. The first one is [...] we have very limited access to synthetic or open health datasets for the technical challenge. I think [we] do the best with what [we] have, but, for me, it seems like a criminal shame that we're the National Health Data Institute and we don't have access to training sets that we can use for training, capacity building of future health data scientists. And then the second side of that is [...] host organisations trying to get access to health datasets for their interns to work on in those eight weeks for their health data project is really hard because it takes so long and it has so many sort of blockades.

Interviewee 1, HDR UK internal member

A related challenge identified by a few participants was host organisations favouring interns with developed quantitative backgrounds. Specifically, some host organisations have high prerequisites of the data skills they are seeking in interns, thereby, excluding people with a qualitative background, for example, or those new to coding. This contradicts one of the main aims of the programme, which is to open up health data science to people from various disciplinary backgrounds.

4.6.3 / External perception of the programme

Although the framing of the programme as a targeted intervention to Black people was mentioned as one of the unique selling points of the BIP, this also featured as a challenge. Some participants stated that this specific focus has generated some push-back, including negative perceptions and divisive comparisons from those questioning why a focus on Black people is prioritised and/or why similar opportunities are not available for other under-represented groups.

I would say, ironically, as much as I said it was a good thing it was named as a Black internship programme, I think sometimes that can bring out negative inferences from people. There's certainly been sort of views among my colleagues like 'why do we need to call it a Black internship programme?'. Because people will focus on the word 'Black'. And sadly, due to the nature of social media, you get the sort of responses of 'oh, there's a Black internship programme, but there's not a White internship one, there's not an Asian one [...].

Interviewee 6, host organisation staff

These reactions have created additional hurdles for the programme's implementation and acceptance in some contexts, as stakeholders struggle with questions of inclusivity versus a targeted intervention for a specific demographic. It is interesting to note, for example, that some participants questioned whether the programme is targeting the right participants to achieve its goal of diversifying the UK health data science sector, referencing the proportion of interns who are international students.

“

I'd be interested in how people are finding the scheme because there's so many foreign students we've had through it as to whether we're doing enough to actually make sure black British people are getting access to the scheme equally.

Interviewee 7, host organisation staff

“

A proportion of interns take part as international students and, ultimately, I don't think that fulfils the aim of BIP of improving UK's health data science community and culture. There may be opportunity to focus on minoritised communities from deprived areas, such as the success in recruiting more interns from non-Russell Group universities.

Host organisation survey respondent 2

Using secondary programme data to check for the validity of these observations, firstly, it is important to highlight that the majority of BIP interns are indeed from non-Russell Group universities (56% of all BIP interns between 2021-2024).

Moreover, the majority of interns that have gone through the programme so far are UK nationals (55%), although there is an increasing trend of a higher proportion of international interns after 2023 (see Figure 20).³

This might be reflective of existing barriers that Black people face into accessing STEM disciplines at the first place (i.e. the small pool of UK Black students in STEM), for example, or that international students have more experience with quantitative skills and are therefore favoured by employers. Dedicated analysis looking across the interns' recruitment cycle (i.e. from application to appointment) in combination with sectoral data for UK Black students in health data science-related fields could shed more light on this area.

Figure 19 / BIP interns' university group background at application stage across time

Figure 20 / BIP interns' nationality breakdown across time

³ Summary tables with the counts and percentages of interns' university group background and nationality status across time can be found in the Appendix, Section 6.8.

4.6.4 / Systemic and structural barriers

Participants raised that the programme encounters challenges related to the very nature of its main goals and objectives. Specifically, the type of changes that the programme aims to make are related to systemic and structural barriers, which require time to manifest and often lie outside the immediate reach of those directly engaging with the programme. For this reason, it is hard to see immediate change. For example, recruitment processes are deeply rooted in historical and institutional practices and need time and synergies across and beyond host organisations to change.

Compounding these difficulties is the programme's position within an increasingly competitive landscape targeting the same 'scarce resource'. The programme must now compete with other similar initiatives to attract the best candidates, creating a situation where multiple programmes may be targeting the same limited pool of talent, which can potentially dilute the programme's quality and impact.

4.6.5 / Workload and time management

The alumni focus groups revealed some challenges related to workload and time management during internships. Some participants described struggling to balance their internship responsibilities with concurrent academic demands, personal commitments and, in some cases, additional employment. In most cases, this was brought up by participants whose internship coincided with particularly intensive academic periods, such as thesis preparation and submission deadlines, creating additional pressure and stress. However, the decision for the BIP internships to take place during the summer period was intentional, as the most likely period for students to be free(er) from academic commitments.

“

The challenge there was that the period of internship is a period for writing your thesis. So, you have a lot of things on your hand.

FG Participant 4, 2024 intern

“

I had to go to the office two or three times, but then the barrier to that was at the time I was a student. So, I have 20 hours [working visa] restriction. It was not just a 20-hour restriction, it was also clashing with the time for my dissertation.

FG Participant 8, 2023 intern

The additional responsibilities and time required by internship placements often left some students feeling overwhelmed and concerned about their ability to meet all obligations to a high standard.

4.6.6 / Logistics, finance and remote working

Some participants revealed logistical and remote-working challenges that impacted their internship experience. Participants reported a few cases in which their internships required lengthy commutes to attend meetings or events, which not only created time pressures but also financial strains, as these travel costs were typically borne by the interns themselves. This financial burden was particularly notable for those interns with limited resources, potentially creating inequitable access to opportunities.

“

I'm based in Sheffield and my main office is in London and then the annex is in Leeds. That means I must take two trains to get to Leeds. If we have an away day in the London office, the company takes care of your transport, but Leeds office, it's on you.

FG Participant 8, 2023 intern

Additionally, the focus groups highlighted that participants who did their internships during the Covid-19 pandemic perceived the remote nature of the BIP offer to be a barrier, as it significantly diminished opportunities for interns to develop networks and reduced exposure to workplace culture and practices.

“

For me it was mainly about Covid [...] I was based in London and my internship was in Cambridge. There were times when I had to do hands-on work at Cambridge, but the centre was closed, so I could not access the centre because of Covid. So, we mainly did everything online. [...] And with the technical challenge group meetings, it would have been nice if we were able to meet face-to-face, but this was not possible because of our geographical positioning, like across different cities in the UK. So, this made it difficult for us to meet in person.

FG participant 17, 2022 intern

4.6.7 / Integration and support from host organisations

A few participants raised challenges relating to organisational structure and support that affected their internship experience. For example, one intern described how they felt a bit awkward, when they realised they had differential access to in-house support and professional development opportunities, compared to another person who was interning within the same host organisation through an internal scheme.

“

There were things that the other interns were afforded that I obviously wasn't. It was a bit odd because obviously they're the same organisation and they're both internship programmes of this organisation, but, like, for example, that their internal interns had a budget for online courses that I wasn't sure if I had access too [...] It would have been nice if I had someone within the organisation that I could go to for clarification, I suppose, about some of these things.

FG participant 3, 2024 intern

There were also a few reports of participants who encountered misunderstandings about their roles and responsibilities within host organisations. These misalignments manifested in various ways, including disconnects between the outputs expected by the host organisation versus HDR UK requirements, or instances where interns received no mentorship.

“

Most people [in my host organisation] didn't really know what other stuff I had to do [...] I think they just expect me to go off and do my own thing and, you know, follow whatever is happening with the job. Also, outputs were not quite meshed together. For example, for the BIP closing ceremony, we had to prepare a presentation. There were end presentations for my internship as a requirement from my host organisation, [too]. But then for BIP, they also encouraged us to do a poster, but I didn't have a poster as a requirement from my host organisation. I could have put some extra time into making one, but it just felt like the end results weren't really meshed together.

FG participant 3, 2024 intern

“

I just remembered that during my time, nobody reached out to me in my organisation to say, 'I'm your mentor'. I don't know if that's the same experience with every other person, but I'm pretty sure where I interned, there were four of us, and nobody had mentorship. You know, it was part of what we're supposed to get.

FG participant 14, 2023 intern

4.7 / Suggestions for improvement

Participants were given the opportunity to raise their suggestions for improvement for the programme at all stages of primary data collection through a dedicated question in the alumni survey. The following topics were raised with regards to improving the internship experience and alumni offer.

4.7.1 / Increased networking opportunities and enhanced mentorship and guidance that exceeds the internship duration

Participants raised that they would like more networking opportunities to connect with sector experts as well as with their peers. They suggested structured networking events as a good way of achieving the former whereas informal meeting opportunities (such as social events) were also suggested to get to know the other interns better. It was clear, though, that any such opportunities would ideally be organised as in-person events.

“

I think adding more structured networking opportunities with professionals across various sectors of health data science could be beneficial. This would allow interns to expand their connections and gain insights into different career paths and specialisations.

Alumni survey participant 7, 2022 intern

Moreover, participants mentioned enhancing the mentorship opportunities to provide more structured guidance and support for interns, ideally in a way that would be sustainable post-internship. This was a point supported by most of the interviewees as well, in terms of what an enhanced post-internship offer should involve. Alumni suggested paired mentorships between interns and experienced professionals (who could be their internship supervisors/managers or other experts) as well as an enhanced alumni mentorship provision, and sustaining those after the internship completion. It should be noted that HDR UK began a pilot alumni mentorship programme in November 2023, which has grown substantially to date. All BIP alumni are eligible to join this programme.

“

While the programme provided some networking avenues, more structured opportunities to connect with professionals from diverse industries, including alumni of the programme, could add significant value. Regular networking events or an alumni mentorship programme would help interns build lasting connections.

Alumni survey respondent 21, 2023 intern

“

The internship should be a sustainable approach to recruitment. If in the case the organisation is not able to recruit the interns they train, they can keep in touch and provide their interns with resources and supports that can help them navigate post-BIP.

Alumni survey respondent 20, 2024 intern

Under the same topic and particularly during focus groups, alumni raised their preference for the enhancement of the alumni mentorship programme, where alumni mentor prospective and/or current interns. Finally, there was general agreement that alumni should maintain engagement with the BIP offer.

4.7.2 / Extension of internship duration and bringing more host organisations on board

Participants in all primary data collection stages raised their preference for the BIP's placement duration to be expanded. After the first year of the programme, initial feedback led to the extension of the internship from 6 to 8 weeks. However, the majority of participants would recommend further extending the duration from 8 to 12 weeks. Interns themselves highlighted that a longer placement would offer them more time to get more valuable work experience as well as to become more integrated within their teams. Host organisation staff on the other hand highlighted that longer placements would allow the interns to be placed on more substantial projects, involving more in-depth perspectives.

“

Yeah, I guess it is quite a short programme. It's only eight weeks and I know obviously that this fits around university term time. So, I'm not sure you can really increase it, but yeah, it's just quite hard to get your teeth stuck into much in eight weeks. [...] We didn't really have like a big kind of research topic that we could give the interns. They're kind of doing smaller things.

Interviewee 10, host organisation staff

The interviews suggested an underlying tension between programme accessibility – keeping duration manageable for participants – and providing an experience of sufficient depth and quality to deliver genuine value, highlighting a fundamental challenge in programme design that staff felt needed careful consideration in future planning. Moreover, all participants expressed that the relatively short timeframe of internships created limitations on relationship development, which they viewed as a critical component of professional growth.

“

I would say there's just like an inherent issue with internship programmes that they're for a finite amount of time. There's a danger, quite rightly, that the interns may go back to their study or go back to their sort of main course of work and not necessarily interact with their organisation. So, there's a danger of kind of losing some of those benefits of the programme because there's only so much you can do with eight weeks, and you're sort of dependent on the intern wanting to stay in touch but also making sure that colleagues within organisations make the time as well.

Interviewee 6, host organisation staff member

“

A longer internship would provide interns with more time to delve deeper into technical tools and methodologies, mastering skills that are essential for industry roles. It would also allow for greater exploration of advanced techniques and tools relevant to their projects. [...] Extending the programme duration will allow interns to immerse themselves in the organisational culture, understand workflows, and contribute more meaningfully to their host organisations. [...] With a longer timeline, interns would have more opportunities to network within the organisation, build lasting connections, and engage in mentorship opportunities, which are critical for career growth.

Alumni survey respondent 21, 2023 intern

4.7.3 / Better support and clarified structure for the technical challenge

A few of the participants highlighted that the technical challenge was quite tricky to balance alongside their internship. This was related with its timing, or the team-based nature of the task and the varied levels of participation noted among the team members. Participants highlighted that they would have welcomed more clarity on the task in advance, the opportunity to pick their own topic, as well as a fairer distribution of technical skills among the different teams.

“

The Technical Challenge is a great initiative, but I think it did not work as well in some groups because it was difficult to determine how much time one could allocate to it with the main projects. I think maybe if roles were assigned within each group, and if there was a check in half-way, it would have been a bit smoother.

Alumni survey respondent 71, 2024 intern

“

Technical challenge was very hard to manage with groups of people with different working patterns and commuting obligations. Work-life balance was not easy to maintain with the additional technical challenge that had to be completed outside of working hours.

Alumni survey respondent 37, 2023 intern

Participants also highlighted interpersonal challenges related to team dynamics, with frustration mostly stemming from inconsistent commitment levels among team members. This lack of equal participation created imbalanced workloads and impeded effective collaboration. Participants noted that team members often failed to communicate their availability, providing “no explanation as to why they are not coming” (FG Participant 6, 2023 intern), creating uncertainty in planning and disrupting workflow continuity.

Finally, participants expressed that technical challenge topics were predetermined without accommodating individual interests or existing skillsets, which limited potential learning opportunities and what, to their eyes, was a fair distribution of skillset among the various teams. As such, a suggested improvement from alumni is to co-create the technical challenges, to achieve a better alignment with their career goals or technical strengths.

“

The technical challenge is something that had been preset – you’re assigned a technical challenge. I think it would be better if we co-create the technical challenge. If the interns co-create the technical challenge, that will mostly speak of whatever skillset that they are lacking that they would like to improve through the technical challenges.

FG Participant 12, 2022 intern

However, as previously mentioned (see section 4.6.2), interviewees highlighted that co-creating the technical challenge topic is almost impossible, due to the restricted access to public health datasets. This shows that interns are unaware of the limited number of open datasets, highlighting an area of awareness-raising and/or training around health data governance, that could help interns understand why this is not possible. Finally, the following quote is reflective of a suggested way through which data accessibility could be improved and the topics of the technical challenges expanded, albeit in the long term, as this is something that would require time and sectoral collaboration:

“

There are some things that can be done. For example, producing synthetic datasets. If we were able to encourage organisations that did hold their data to produce synthetic datasets, that would cover some of the issues. [...] People are considering it. I’ve not seen anyone push hard in that direction and I’ve not seen it done in a coordinated way, [...] but that would really help us for the technical challenge, because we already rely on one or two datasets, but we’ve probably done everything we can do with them. We have noticed that NHS has just sort of released an extra one. It’s quite basic, but it shows that they’re starting to do a bit more with it. So, there’s probably more that can be done in that space.

Interviewee 3, HDR UK internal member

4.7.4 / Additional skills development and training provided

The provision of additional training sessions focused on both technical and transferrable skills to better prepare interns for further career pathways was another area within suggestions for improvement. Responses coded under this theme focused mainly on examples of training sessions focused on technical skills relevant to data science and health data research, but also on soft skills, such as understanding the corporate environment and navigating career pathways.

“

Structured sessions focusing on career guidance, personalised feedback and connecting interns with industry leaders could have enhanced the experience. Additionally, incorporating workshops on emerging trends in AI and data science for healthcare, such as generative AI, federated learning or ethical AI, would have been valuable for expanding our technical knowledge.

Alumni survey respondent 105, 2023 intern

“

I think incorporating a one-time seminar focused on mainly on the current challenges in health data science, along with emerging technologies such as AI, would significantly enhance the learning experience.

Alumni survey respondent 7, 2022 intern

With regards to improving the host organisation offer, the following topics were raised:

4.7.5 / More guidance and clarity in terms of what participation in the programme really means for host organisations

Responses under this theme focused on the need for clearer communications in terms of what benefits participation in the BIP will yield for the host organisation. Some suggestions of what this could entail include the creation of a repository of BIP alumni, which host organisations could use to draw from once they had open vacancies, as well as another repository with host organisations who opt in to share their contact details with other host organisations, so that networking could be encouraged.

“

It would be good to have some form of directory where internship alumni could put their details, skills expertise, availability date etc and when host organisations have opportunities become available, they could then pull from that pool.

Host organisation survey respondent 24

4.7.6 / Information sheet for host organisation staff on the topics and timings of interns' trainings and major deadlines

In relation to the previous theme, host organisation staff seemed to also be in favour of more succinct information on the content and timing of training and major deadlines that interns had to meet, so that they could have better oversight of the whole process and provide them with better support. Although one participant highlighted that the training sessions offered to interns by the BIP were included in the host organisation handbook, they noted that “it wasn't that easy to find [a] clear summary” (Host organisation survey respondent 29).

“

I found it difficult to follow exactly what the interns were doing as part of their weekly training with the BIP. It would be good for the hosts to be able to engage with the intern a bit more on this so they can find ways in which to support them and the intern can feel more comfortable in asking for advice in any aspect of that training. Maybe an information sheet for the hosts on what's covered in the training sessions and timings of any project deadlines.

Host organisation survey respondent 14

4.7.7 / Modifications in interns' selection and recruitment processes

Participants were keen to adapt the way in which interns are selected and recruited. Answers coded under this theme involved moving towards an interest-based matching of applicants with host organisations (for example, identifying applicants expressing an interest to work “charity vs NHS vs pharma vs industry” and placing them accordingly), but also raised a need for guidance and transparency on how to most effectively select interns. Specifically, a few participants mentioned that they had identified some of the interns using AI tools during their applications and would thus like to include some technical tests as part of their selection process.

Greater guidance and openness on intern selection and programme commitments, more lessons learned documentation and sharing between host organisations on how to get around processes and what worked well and what didn't. Technical test to be added.

Host organisation survey respondent 11

Finally, in terms of looking at what the BIP could do to evolve in the future, two main themes were identified:

4.7.8 / Expanding the provision to engage with other marginalised groups, and considerations for targeting specific groups

Participants suggested tailoring the provision to either engage with wider audiences or to focus on specific sub-groups of Black students (such as UK Black students). In terms of the former, they suggested that HDR UK could either run “sister schemes” or extend the BIP to engage with other marginalised communities. For the latter, as mentioned previously, there were specific mentions to “minoritised communities from deprived areas, such as [...] more interns from non-Russell Group universities” as an area of focus. Intersectional considerations were also raised by host organisation survey respondents and interviewees as an additional area worth of investigating. For example, a participant suggested that an intersectional analysis into the diverse pathways from which people end up in the field of health data science could help HDR UK target its efforts, an opinion that was also shared by a couple of the interviewees.

Health data science is an intersection of several fields. At the core of each of those fields there are maybe different diversity issues. [...] Most entrants into health data use one of these doors, and then transition [...] I think understanding these avenues, their demographics and possible filters would really help the BIP team engage in the right way, with the right people and orgs, at the right point in time.

Host organisation survey respondent 15

4.7.9 / Access to additional funding and enhanced advocacy for diversification of health data science

Some host organisation staff highlighted that they would welcome some additional financial support to sustain their engagement with the programme. This could either happen through additional funds from the HDR UK team or through government funding.

“

It is very time-intensive and expensive for host organisations to participate. There seems to be no national support for this, except in academic institutions. It would be good if HDR UK could use the results of this survey to lobby for the government to provide financial support to continue such programmes.

Host organisation survey respondent 9

Similarly, alumni mentioned their wish to see HDR UK and the BIP advocate more widely for the diversification of the sector. They suggested that this could happen through using the alumni community and publishing case studies focusing on showcasing career journeys post-internship as well as through collaborating with government and funding bodies to support Black people's access to academic journeys in health data science fields.

“

I think an option is to explore if there are available pots of funding from kind of the government for HDR UK and the BIP to support the diversification of higher education, for example. Because a lot of us from this internship we've then gone on to doing a PhD, I'm also studying at the moment. So that can be a direct link of actually taking people who have shown themselves to be kind of excellent in a way through their internships to then propel them forward into academic roles. As we know that academia at the moment is not a very diverse kind of place to be, especially in the UK right now, [...], just maybe more of a connection between the government funding research and connecting to students who might actually want to go further in their education, aside from just the internship, to higher education.

FG participant 10, 2022 intern

This idea of the BIP exploring interventions at different stages of the employment career continuum to address the under-representation of Black people was also endorsed by several interviewees, raising, for example, linking the programme with secondary education or feeding into the curricula of university courses, so that the next generation of health data scientists have the skills that employers want and are currently lacking.

“

I think if I were to have like ambitions on what a programme could do further, it would be exploring the sort of health data scientist journey either side of it. So, how you recruit people into the field from schools into university courses or how well people progress once they are in the job.

Interviewee 3, HDR UK internal member

5

Summative review of evidence found for BIP's outcomes and impact

Evidence for all of outcomes identified in the theory of change (see Figure 2 in section 2.1), were traced during the primary data collection for this review. The programme's core strengths include high levels of satisfaction among alumni and host organisations, who describe a structured learning experience, enhancing participants' data as well as transferable skills, and a holistic approach, offering mentorship as well as training, alongside hands-on practical experience with health data science real-world problems. Host organisations gain access to a diverse talent pool, as participation in the BIP offers a cost-effective recruitment process. Moreover, host organisation staff benefit from engagement with the programme via an increased understanding of the challenges Black early-career researchers face as well as of the benefits that including their perspectives has for effectively tackling health data science issues.

The programme's impact on further career pathways is probably its biggest success in terms fulfilling its objective of increasing the representation of Black people in the sector. It is evident that the BIP raises alumni aspirations to engage further with the (health) data science sector, with 43% of the total alumni survey respondents continuing their education and/or getting a job in health data science, health technology or data science following their internship. Importantly, alumni attribute their further career progression to their engagement with the BIP. Host organisation staff also agree that interns are more 'job-ready' after going through BIP.

The following table visually represents the volume of evidence found for each of the outcomes identified during the theory of change co-construction stage for interns and host organisations. Specifically, the table indicates in which of the primary data collection

sources evidence was found for each outcome. Outcomes have been colour-coded using a traffic light system, with green indicating high volume of evidence, amber medium and red low.

Outcome by key target group	Alumni survey	Host org survey	Alumni focus groups	Key stakeholder interviews
BIP interns				
Improved data skills	✓	✓	✓	✓
Increased knowledge and understanding of health data science (HDS) sector	✓	✓	✓	✓
High-quality field experience through their internship gained	✓	✓	✓	✓
Increased self-confidence	✓		✓	✓
Improved, meaningful insights into career opportunities in HDS	✓	✓	✓	✓
Heightened growth mindset	✓		✓	✓
Increased perceptions of being 'job ready' compared to before BIP engagement		✓	✓	
Pursue aspirations to continue their careers/ education in HDS either in UK or abroad	✓		✓	✓
Alumni secure jobs/continue their education in HDS sector	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sustained engagement with BIP post internship	✓		✓	✓
Follow-on networks and collaborations between alumni and/or host organisations	✓	✓	✓	✓
Host organisations				
Increased awareness of the value of diverse staff		✓	✓	✓
Perceive BIP alumni as job ready		✓	✓	✓
Draw from the BIP alumni pool for further employment opportunities		✓	✓	✓
Sustained engagement with BIP		✓		✓
Improved recruitment policies and practices to attract minoritised candidates		✓		✓
Improved support systems in place for minoritised staff				✓

Although impact falls outside of the scope of the current review, as this normally extends the total duration of an intervention, evidence of impact was found for some of the statements included under this section of the theory of change in just the four years since the BIP was established. The following table illustrates the volume

of evidence traced during the primary data collection methods and the secondary analysis conducted using programme data provided by the BIP team as part of this review, for each of the impacts identified during the theory of change co-creation. A traffic light system has also been used here for colour-coding.

Impact item	Secondary data analysis	Alumni survey	Host org survey	Alumni focus groups	Key stakeholder interviews
Increased awareness of BIP across time among each target populations, which leads to increased interest in, and value attached to the programme.	✓			✓	✓
Increased awareness of racial inequities and biases within and beyond the health data science sector.			✓		✓
HDR UK established as a thought leader in advancing the careers of under-represented groups in health data science.	✓				✓
HDR UK's established reputation as producing and sharing good practice around inclusive recruitment and developing support practices for the health data science sector.	✓				✓
BIP and its findings inspire similar provisions from other sectoral organisations (e.g. LIDA).	✓				✓
Improved approach of health data science organisations regarding recruitment and support of Black people.					
Improved representation of Black people in the UK health data science sector.	✓				
BIP alumni have accelerated career advancement (e.g. attain senior roles).		✓		✓	

Specifically, there was evidence for the increasing reputation and value attached to the programme from prospective interns and host organisations as well as the wider sector. Moreover, the programme's awareness-raising capabilities, mostly with regards to the disparities that Black scientists face within the health data science sector were highlighted by host organisation staff and wider sectoral experts. It was also encouraging that some interviewees pinpointed specific initiatives the BIP had influenced, such

as ringfencing a set number of positions for racially minoritised people at the University of Leeds' Institute for Data Analytics Data Science Development Programme, or the Black in Cancer mentorship programme. Finally, some of the BIP alumni indicated having already attained senior level roles (such as Senior Health Scientist, Senior Information Analyst), sometimes mentioning accelerated progression, with quicker promotions or higher-level salaries achieved due to their BIP projects and skills accomplished.

6

Conclusion and recommendations

A co-created theory of change was used as the logic model for this programme evaluation. The theory of change identified the key outputs, outcomes and impact the programme was envisaged to deliver for its key target audiences (i.e. interns, host organisations) as well as for HDR UK and the wider health data science sector.

Findings are clearly positive in terms of both process and impact evaluation, with the programme being delivered as anticipated, and strong evidence found to support the expected outcomes within the four-year time period under review.

Specifically, the BIP is a programme with increasing demand as time passes. This is evidenced by the rising numbers of:

- + Applicants to the programme and
- + Host organisations engaging with the programme across time

Undoubtedly, major contributors to BIP's successes are:

- + Alumni's perceptions of the programme as beneficial for their skills development and subsequent career progression
- + Host organisation's satisfaction with the interns and the programme offer and
- + The BIP team's dedication and commitment to provide an offer of the utmost quality to both host organisations and interns

However, some challenges with the programme are evident. Most commonly raised were concerns regarding the programme's sustainability and scalability at its current staffing and financial state. Limitations related to the short duration of the internships and dataset accessibility, as well as occasional inconsistent mentorship, logistical constraints and varying levels of support across host organisations, also need to be addressed.

Moving forward, strategic decision-making needs to take place. This will happen as the programme is now entering a period of strategic planning for its next phase. During this period, areas such as how to enhance the programme's sustainability, strengthen its long-term outcomes, and ensure that host organisations are well-equipped to provide meaningful experiences for interns should be considered. With targeted refinements, HDR UK's BIP can continue to provide an inclusive internship programme that contributes to diversifying the health data science workforce.

Although suggestions for improvement have already been identified by the participants of this review, below are key recommendations for consideration for the future of the BIP, which can help the programme further amplify its success and ensure long-term impact and sustainability, whilst fostering an inclusive and diverse health data science community.

6.1 / Co-design the next phase of the programme with key stakeholders

This review has shown that the first four years of the BIP have been a great success, galvanising a strong project team who offer top-quality support to applicants, interns, alumni and host organisations alike, whilst also trying to grow. However, as outlined above, capacity is currently stretched. The BIP's future direction of travel should be co-designed by the variety of key stakeholders involved in the programme. There needs to be an agreement on what the BIP wants to achieve, before the future of the programme can be shaped. The review has provided evidence that could support either the expansion of the project through both scaling up and branching out, or the retainment of this tight-knit community between interns and the supportive relationship that smaller-scale projects allow for in terms of managing applicants, interns, alumni and host organisations in a more personalised way. Collaborative decision-making through evidence-informed insights will provide the answer to this dilemma. This review forms the basis of a collection of relevant evidence, but conducting a return of investment analysis, incorporating elements of a cost-benefit approach could also be considered, to further shape a robust understanding of the current and future commercial value and standing of the BIP.

6.2 / Expand the delivery team's capacity and increase the resilience of the host organisation pipeline

For the programme to grow to meet some of the extensive increase in demand for places demonstrated in section 4.6.1, we recommend expanding the programme team to provide additional capacity for coordinating, supporting, managing and expanding relationships with interns and host organisations, as well as for monitoring and evaluating the programme. With current capacity being stretched, it is of paramount importance to avoid single points of failure both for internal processes (for example, leadership of different parts of the BIP offer), as well as for external activities, such as establishing strong relationships with host organisations, which do not rely on single contact points. This will be key to ensuring the programme's sustainability and a prerequisite for expanding the programme any further.

Along similar lines, exploring options for long-term funding is important. External sponsors, government funding as well as funding councils and partnerships are all possible avenues, but there needs to be focused discussions in terms of identifying realistic options.

6.3 / Strengthen external communications to further promote the programme's impact and clarify the host organisation offer

The review has outlined that the BIP is a successful and unique initiative, with beneficial outcomes for the interns and host organisations who engage with it. However, it has also been identified that pinpointing those outcomes in a standardised way has so far been a challenge, mainly due to resource limitations. This programme has achieved remarkable successes and has much to celebrate. Review participants have recommended making better use of alumni career stories, host organisation staff testimonials, and sector experts' opinion pieces to amplify the programmes visibility and showcase its impact.

Most importantly, the BIP offer needs to be further clarified for host organisations. Outlining the main benefits from participation, such as an increased awareness of the benefit of a diverse workforce, access to a talent pool of job-ready employees, insights into how to move towards inclusive recruitment practices and working cultures, as well as the opportunity to offer management experience to staff members who do not officially hold such roles, is just a sample of what the BIP has to offer. In a time where most organisations have to be financially prudent, BIP has to frame itself clearly as an initiative that is not only centred around EDI and social justice principles, but also has real employability benefits. The long-term sustainability of the programme is dependent on having a variety of hosts engaged with it, who can offer interns quality and insightful real-world working experiences. A clearly defined host organisation offer in combination with dedicated capacity for host organisation relationship management will help maximise engagement through spreading both out and upwards.

6.4 / Continue to focus on feedback, monitoring and evaluation

The BIP's strength comes from its resilience and flexibility, which is built on a robust system of acting on feedback and learning from previous experiences through an emphasis on continuous monitoring and evaluation. This review, including the formation of a ToC and the collection of evidence regarding the programme's process and impact evaluation, has further contributed to embedding monitoring and evaluation in the BIP, offering a basis for tracking where the programme is, as well as a platform through which to (re)design the next phase of the programme.

Successful initiatives are tied to robust evaluation and the BIP has already been following this trajectory. A continuous focus on designing, communication and using robust feedback mechanisms, allowing both interns and host organisations to provide their input at different time points, will be essential

to maintaining an evidence base. Moreover, as the programme progresses, different aspects will become more prominent. For example, long-term outcomes and impact will be gaining attention, with elements such as long-term tracking of the alumni's career pathways or a review of the practices used to engage both interns and host organisations in BIP becoming prevalent. Ensuring that systematic impact assessment tools are in place to help with the monitoring of these aspects is an important area of consideration for future rounds of evaluation.

The central purpose of this review was to establish whether the programme is both effective and relevant. It has found the answer to be strongly positive on both counts. The under-representation of Black people in health data sciences remains a pertinent issue and BIP's role in upskilling and bridging Black talented individuals with sectoral organisations to facilitate more conducive relationships is of great importance. We close this report with the words of a BIP alumna, who powerfully sums up what the programme is achieving for its interns:

“

This is one of the only opportunities you have as a Black person in data science, in health, data science, in tech, to be fully, authentically Black without fear of judgement or whatever, or fear of being misunderstood. [...] Everyone who has passed through the programme, at least people I've interacted with who have passed through the programme, have the programme as a pivotal point in their career. It's a community of people who look like you, who speak like you, who think like you, who have the same experiences you've had. So, yeah, that's, that's really where the passion comes from.

FG participant 18, 2023 intern

7 Appendix

7.1 / Acknowledgements

The Advance HE research team would like to extend a big thank you to the HDR UK Black Internship Programme core team for bringing us onboard to this wonderful project, for making us always feel included and welcomed, and for all their support and collaboration throughout this evaluation journey.

The Advance HE researchers, in tandem with the HDR UK Black Internship Programme team, would also like to express our deepest gratitude to all the participants who engaged with this evaluation. These involve Black Internship Programme alumni, host organisation staff, advisory board members, HDR UK staff members and health data science sector experts. Carving time out of people's busy schedules

to devote to a programme evaluation is work that should be praised and acknowledged, as it shows genuine care. For this reason, this is a recognition of all our participants for sharing their perceptions and experiences with us; without them, this report would have never materialised. A special mention needs to be made of the 98 host organisations who partnered with the Black Internship Programme between the years in scope of this review (2021-2024), as it is their engagement and participation that made this programme possible and shaped the experiences of the interns. Naming these organisations in the following alphabetical list is the smallest gesture to honour their contribution:

- + Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK)
- + Alan Turing Institute
- + Alzheimer's Society
- + Barts Health NHS Trust – Queen Mary University of London
- + Big Data Institute, University of Oxford
- + Brain Tumour Charity
- + British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre
- + British Red Cross
- + British United Provident Association (BUPA)
- + Brunel University London – College of Health Medicine and Life Sciences
- + Cancer Research UK
- + Cancer Research UK Cambridge Institute
- + Cancer Research UK Oxford Centre
- + Centre for Healthcare Modelling and Informatics
- + Centre for Trials Research Cardiff University
- + Children with Cancer UK
- + Coventry and Warwickshire NHS Trust
- + Cystic Fibrosis Trust
- + Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK)
- + Data Connect at the University of Sheffield
- + DATA-CAN: The Health Data Research Hub for Cancer
- + Department of Health and Social Care
- + Digital Research Service, University of Nottingham
- + East Suffolk and North Essex NHS Foundation Trust
- + EMBL-EBI (The European Bioinformatics Institute) – Cambridge
- + Environment Agency
- + Genomics England
- + Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust
- + HDR UK / Medical Schools Council

- + HDR UK Technology team
- + Health Data Research Breathe Hub
- + Health Data Research Gut Reaction Hub
- + Health Informatics Centre, University of Dundee
- + Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust
- + Imperial College Healthcare Partners
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: Imperial College London
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: Alder Hey Children's NHS Foundation Trust
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: Clinical Practice Research Datalink
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: Queen's University Belfast
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: Swansea University
- + Inflammation and Immunity Driver Programme: The University of Edinburgh
- + Innovations in Development, Education and the Mathematical Sciences (IDEMS) International Community Interest Company
- + Intensive Care National Audit & Research Centre (ICNARC)
- + King's College London
- + London North West NHS Trust
- + London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine
- + Manchester Hospitals NHS Trust
- + Mary Lyon Centre / MRC Harwell
- + Moderna
- + National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE)
- + National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) BioResource
- + National Institute for Health and Care Research Clinical Research Network (NIHR CRN)
- + NHS National Services Scotland
- + NHS Blood and Transplant
- + NHS Digital
- + NHS Elect
- + Nuffield Trust
- + Office for National Statistics
- + Our Future Health
- + Picker Institute Europe
- + PIONEER – The Health Data Research Hub for Acute Care
- + Public Health Scotland
- + Rosalind Franklin Institute
- + SAIL Databank, Swansea University
- + Swansea University
- + The Health Economics Unit
- + The Health Foundation
- + The King's Fund
- + The Norfolk and Norwich University Hospitals NHS
- + The UK MS Register, Swansea University
- + UCL (Advanced Research Computing Centre/ Institute of Child Health /Institute of Health Informatics /Institute of Healthcare Engineering / MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing)
- + UCL Partners
- + UK Health Security Agency
- + UK Kidney Association
- + University Hospitals Birmingham, University of Birmingham
- + University of Birmingham
- + University of Birmingham / Google Deep Mind
- + University of Bristol
- + University of Cambridge

- + University of Edinburgh

- + University of Exeter

- + University of Glasgow

- + University of Lancaster

- + University of Leicester – Real World Evidence

- + University of Manchester – Manchester Cancer Research Centre

- + University of Nottingham

- + University of Oxford (Bennett Institute for Applied Data Science / Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences / Nuffield Population Health)

- + University of Southampton

- + Wellcome Connecting Science

- + Wellcome Sanger Institute / HDR UK Cambridge

- + Wellcome-MRC Cambridge Stem Cell Institute

- + Wolverhampton NHS Trust

- + Yorkshire and Humber Academic Health Science Network

7.2 / Description of the alumni survey sample

Of the 111 responses received from the past interns' survey, the majority came from the last two years' cohorts, which is to be expected, as older participants are always harder to engage in such exercises. Aside from that, the response percentage from each cohort is roughly proportional to the size of each cohort. The following table outlines this more clearly.

In terms of their status when they joined the BIP, most of the survey respondents indicated they were Master's students (48.6%). In second place came recent graduates (24.3% of the total survey respondents), whereas 21.6% of the respondents said they were doing their undergraduate studies when they joined the programme. The remaining respondents were PhD or returning students.

In terms of their main field of studies when they engaged with the programme, most of the survey respondents came from Engineering and Technology (45%), with those from Medicine, Dentistry and Health Sciences following (28.8%) and an additional 24.3% coming from Biological, Mathematical and Physical Sciences. The remaining 2% came from Social Studies or from an unidentified field of studies.

Survey respondents were asked what region of the UK they were based in at the time they applied to take part in the BIP. Although, as expected, the majority of interns were based in London, there are BIP interns across the UK, and it is noticeable that the second most popular base for interns is the Yorkshire and Humber area.

Table 1 / Participants and survey responses by cohort

	Total interns	Percentage of total interns	Survey respondents	Percentage of total survey respondents
2021	47	15.3%	16	14.4%
2022	79	25.6%	24	21.6%
2023	89	28.9%	34	30.6%
2024	93	30.2%	37	33.3%

7.2.1 / Sociodemographic characteristics

Table 2 summarises the main attributes of the survey respondents, comparing those to information available from the total number of BIP interns, where data is available.

Although the survey respondents are proportional to the total BIP interns in terms of sex, this is not the case in terms of their nationality status, where in the survey there are many more international respondents participating (82% non-UK citizens in the survey sample in comparison to 45% non-UK citizens in all BIP interns). In the sample, there were 18 different nationalities represented, with Nigeria being the most popular category (55.9% of survey participants), reflecting what happens among the total BIP interns, where Nigeria is the most popular category for non-UK interns (31% of the total BIP interns indicate being Nigerian citizens).

7.2.2 / Host organisations

Of the 98 organisations which have hosted BIP interns across its four years of operation, we received survey responses from interns who had been based in 53 of those. The top five host organisations represented among the survey respondents were:

- A.** The National Institute for Health Research BioResource studies (NIHR BioResource) and Clinical Research Network (eight responses)
- B.** Department of Health and Social Care, the Rosalind Franklin Institute and the University of Cambridge (six responses each)
- C.** University College London (UCL) (five responses)

These are all organisations which feature in the top 10 of host organisations with the highest number of interns, although not in this order.

A full list with the host organisations where the survey respondents indicated being based is provided in the following table.

Table 2 / Survey sample sociodemographic make-up and comparisons with total BIP interns

	Survey respondents	Total BIP interns
Sex	67 female (60.4%), 44 male (39.7%)	188 female (61%), 120 male (39%)
Nationality	19 UK citizens (17.1%), 91 non-UK citizens (82%), 1 prefer not to say	169 UK citizens (55%), 139 non-UK citizens (45%)
First-generation university entrant status	78 (70.3%) no, 31 (27.9%) yes, 2 (1.8%) prefer not to say	Information not available

Table 3 / Past intern survey respondents by host organisation

Host organisation	Number of respondents
NIHR BioResource / CRN (Clinical Research Network)	8
Department of Health and Social Care	6
Rosalind Franklin Institute	6
University of Cambridge	6
UCL (Institute of Child Health /Institute of Health Informatics /Institute of Healthcare Engineering /MRC Unit for Lifelong Health and Ageing, ARC)	5
LSHTM (London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine)	4
Public Health Scotland	4
Swansea University / SAIL Databank	4
UK Health Security Agency	4
University of Dundee – Health Informatics Centre	4
BUPA (British United Provident Association)	3
Cancer Research UK	3
Genomics England	3
Our Future Health	3
UCL Partners	3
University of Oxford – Big Data Institute	3
Alan Turing Institute	2
BHF (British Heart Foundation) Data Science Centre	2
British Red Cross	2
Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust	2
Queen Mary University London – Barts Health NHS Trust	2
University of Edinburgh	2
ADR UK (Administrative Data Research UK)	1
Alzheimer’s Society	1
Brain Tumour Charity	1

Host organisation	Number of respondents
Cancer Research UK – Cambridge Institute	1
Children with Cancer	1
DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK)	1
DATA-CAN: The Health Data Research Hub for Cancer	1
East Suffolk and North Essex NHS Foundation Trust	1
Guy's and St Thomas' NHS Foundation Trust	1
HDR UK – Medical Schools Council	1
HDR UK – Technology Team	1
Health Data Research Breathe Hub	1
IDEMS (Innovations in Development, Education and the Mathematical Sciences) International	1
Imperial College London	1
Mary Lyon Centre / MRC Harwell	1
NHS – National Services Scotland	1
NHS Digital	1
Queen's University Belfast	1
The Health Foundation	1
The Norfolk and Norwich University Hospitals NHS	1
UK Kidney Association	1
University of Exeter	1
University of Glasgow	1
University of Lancaster	1
University of Manchester – Manchester Cancer Research Centre	1
University of Nottingham – Digital Research Service	1
University of Oxford	1
University of Southampton	1
Wolverhampton NHS Trust	1
Yorkshire and Humber Academic Health Science Network	1

7.2.3 / Internship type

Out of the 111 survey respondents, 52 indicated having done a remote internship (46.9%), an equal amount a hybrid one and only seven (6.3%) indicated that they completed their internship fully in person. The following table outlines the type of internships completed across each cohort, showing that, besides in-person only opportunities, which did not feature at all in 2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic, all types of internships are present across each cohort.

Moreover, 72% of survey respondents indicated that their internship was full-time, with the remaining stating it was part-time. None of the 2021 respondents indicated having done a part-time option, and full-time internships are the majority across all cohorts. Finally, in terms of the duration of the respondents' internships, the majority were eight weeks long (65.8%), 20.7% were 12 weeks long, 9% lasted over 12 weeks and 1.8% for less than eight weeks.

Table 4 / Type of internships completed by survey respondents by BIP cohort

	2021	2022	2023	2024
Hybrid internship	25%	50%	53%	49%
In-person internship	0%	4%	9%	8%
Remote internship	75%	46%	38%	43%
Total survey respondents	16	24	34	37

7.2.4 / Internship location

The 59 survey respondents who indicated having completed either a fully in-person or a hybrid internship were called to indicate to which region of the UK they had to travel when going to their internship offices.

The majority of survey respondents (61%) indicated that their internship offices were in the region in which they were located when they applied for the opportunity. For the remaining 39%, London was a popular area for travel to attend their offices (41% of

the 29 interns having to attend London offices were not from London), followed by the East of England (83% of the six interns having to attend offices there were from elsewhere), and the North West (60% of the five interns having to attend offices there were from elsewhere).

The table in the following page outlines how many interns were local or had to travel from other areas to attend their internship offices.

Table 5 / BIP internship offices' location by area of residence when applying for the BIP

BIP internship office locations	Interns based in the same area (% of total interns in the area)	Interns based in different area (% of total interns in the area)
East Midlands	1 (50%)	London: 1 (50%)
East of England	1 (16.7%)	London: 4 (66.6%) North East: 1(16.7%)
London	17 (58.6%)	East Midlands: 4 (13.8%) Yorkshire: 3 (10.3%) Wales: 2 (6.9%) West Midlands: 1 (3.4%) Scotland: 1 (3.4%) South East: 1 (3.4%)
North East	1 (100%)	
North West	2 (40%)	North East: 1 (20%) Yorkshire: 2 (40%)
Northern Ireland	1 (100%)	
Scotland	2 (100%)	
South East	2 (50%)	London: 1 (25%) Yorkshire: 1(25%)
South West	1 (100%)	
Wales	1 (100%)	
West Midlands	1 (100%)	
Yorkshire	6 (100%)	

7.3 / Description of the host organisation staff survey sample

The survey received responses from staff members from 25 out of the 98 host organisations that have ever participated in the BIP. In most cases, one staff member responded from each host organisation. However, there were three cases in which more than one staff member responded from a single

organisation (i.e. two responses from Nuffield Trust and University of Leicester's Real World Evidence and three responses from the UK Health Security Agency). A full list of the host organisations at which the survey respondents indicated being based is provided in the table in the following page.

Table 6 / Host organisation staff survey respondents by host organisation

Host organisation	Number of respondents
UK Health Security Agency	3
Nuffield Trust	2
University of Leicester – Real World Evidence	2
BHF (British Heart Foundation) Data Science Centre	1
Cancer Research UK	1
Cystic Fibrosis Trust	1
DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK)	1
Department of Health and Social Care	1
Genomics England	1
HDR UK – Medical Schools Council	1
Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust	1
Inflammation and Immunity Research Driver Programme – Swansea University	1
LSHTM (London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine)	1
Manchester Hospitals NHS Trust	1
Mary Lyon Centre / MRC Harwell	1
NICE (National Institute for Health and Care Excellence)	1
Rosalind Franklin Institute	1
The Health Foundation	1
The King's Fund	1
The Norfolk and Norwich University Hospitals NHS	1
UCL Partners	1
University of Bristol	1
University of Edinburgh	1
University of Glasgow	1
University of Manchester – Manchester Cancer Research Centre	1

From the 25 host organisations represented in the survey, seven participated in the BIP only in one year (28%), and in most of those cases, this was 2024 (six out of seven).

The following table outlines the percentage of host organisations represented among the survey responses and how many of those participated in each year of the BIP:

Table 7 / Host organisations represented across survey responses and their BIP participation rates across time

Year of cohort	Percentage of host organisation participating (out of the 25 represented across survey respondents)
2021	24%
2022	48%
2023	72%
2024	88%

7.4 / Description of the online focus groups sample

Seventeen participants engaged with the three online focus groups conducted. The following table provides an outline of when each section was conducted and how many alumni engaged with each one of those.

There was representation across all cohorts, student statuses and disciplinary backgrounds within the focus group sample, but the following table provides a detailed breakdown of the sociodemographic and background characteristics of the 17 focus group participants.

Table 8 / Alumni distribution per online focus group session

Session 1: 24 January 2025 – 3:30-5pm	5 participants
Session 2: 27 January 2025 – 5:30-7pm	8 participants
Session 3: 29 January 2025 – 12-1:30pm	4 participants
Total	17 participants

Table 9 / Online focus group participants' sociodemographic and background characteristics breakdown

Cohort representation	2021: 18% 2022: 29% 2023: 29% 2024: 24%
Status when joined the BIP	Undergraduate: 12% Master's: 53% PhD: 12% Recent graduate: 18% Returning student: 6%
Main disciplinary background when joined the BIP	Biological, mathematical and physical sciences: 24% Engineering and technology: 29% Medicine, dentistry and health: 41% Social studies: 6%
Sex	Female: 59% Male: 41%
First generation university entrant status	Yes: 35% No: 65%
Internship length	8 weeks: 59% More than 8 weeks: 41%
Internship status	Full-time: 59% Part-time: 41% Hybrid: 71% Remote: 24% In-person: 6%
Number of host organisations represented across focus group participants	15

7.5 / Online interviewees participant breakdown

Eleven one-to-one online interviews were conducted as part of this review.

The table below provides the breakdown of participants in each one of the four categories used for sampling.

Table 10 / Online interviewees participant breakdown

Stakeholder group	Number of participants
HDR UK internal members	4
HDR UK BIP advisory board members	2
Host organisation members	3
Health data science sector experts	2

7.6 / A Top-level overview of other programmes not included in the desk-based review

Programme	Organisation	Target	Main aims and objectives	Conflict of Interest	Start	Yearly cohort size	Length	Location
Biomedical Vacation Scholarship	Wellcome	All second/ third year undergraduate students, but prioritisation for under-represented groups	These awards provide promising undergraduates with hands-on experience of research during the summer holidays, with the aim of encouraging them to consider a career in research	HDR UK delivers this	2021	~4	6-8 weeks, summer	Across UK
Digital Fellowship	Shuri Network, NHS England	Women from ethnic minorities in NHS professional groups (Band 5-8a)	Empower individuals to overcome career-related challenges, gain insight into different digital roles, build positive relationships and self-confidence. Sessions include digital and data experts to increase your knowledge and understanding of digital topics, innovation and implementation of change	None	2021 (4th cohort 2024-25)	~20	September – May, part-time	
Black Leaders in Diabetes	Diabetes UK, Windsor Foundation	Black Home Science undergraduates in penultimate / final year or a current MSc student, or graduates (3 years)	To give experience of undertaking research within the field of diabetes in the UK to science undergraduates from Black backgrounds and to encourage them to consider a career in scientific research	Approached on providing feedback / recommendations during the planning stage	2024	N/A	6 weeks, summer	Across UK

Programme	Organisation	Target	Main aims and objectives	Conflict of Interest	Start	Yearly cohort size	Length	Location
Health Analytics Postgraduate Internship	Lane, Clark and Peacock (LCP)	ECR all 2:1 STEM degree or better in a numerate or scientific subject or Medical degree and MSc/ PhD preferable	Working with real world data sources, planning and carrying out analyses using R, SQL or Python, and helping to turn results into insights for our clients by creating data visualisations and writing reports and scientific publications	None	2020	Unknown	10 weeks, Autumn	Across UK
Data Science internship scheme for innovation and analytics in health	NHS England	PhD student working in a quantitative discipline	An opportunity to work on and support real time research analytics in an industrial setting, with access to NHS data, which may ultimately impact on patient services	None	Unknown	Unknown	3-5 months	Across UK
Health Data Insight CIC Internship Programme	Health Data Insight CIC	ECR all	Develop an innovative digital and/or physical solution using data which will make a difference to the healthcare system	Using Simulacrum data in technical challenge	2016	Unknown	2-3 months, summer	DI offices in CamLife/ Capital Park, Fulbourn, Cambridge
Strive Internship UK	Hargreaves Lansdown (British financial services company based in Bristol, England)	Black, Asian and minority ethnic university students	Offers paid work experience placements. Internships offer opportunities for students to fully immerse themselves in placements with partner organisations	Unknown	2020	30	6–8 weeks, gaining hands-on experience, building confidence, and learning new skills.	West of England
Diversity Summer Internship Programme for Undergraduates (USA)	The Bloomberg School of Public Health, Johns Hopkins University	Students from under-represented groups and diverse backgrounds, including individuals with disabilities, individuals from economically disadvantaged backgrounds, and women	Provides highly qualified undergraduates with a graduate-level research experience in the biomedical or public health field. Additionally, interns engage in professional leadership development focused on developing critical thinking, collaboration, and communication skills Interns are mentored by accomplished Johns Hopkins researchers	None	2012	Unknown	8-week summer programme	Undergraduate students (US citizens or permanent residents) enrolled in a degree-seeking programme within a US college or university are eligible to apply
Clyde Miller Career Academy	Saint Louis University in conjunction with the Jost Chemical Company	Minority students	Work directly with university faculty on research projects. The students gain knowledge of chemistry and laboratory procedures. After successful completion of the program, the students receive paid internships at Jost Chemical during the summer after they graduate from high school	None	2013	Unknown	Summer program	St Louis school district
Health Disparities Summer Internship Program (HDSIP)	University of Alabama	High school students of colour	The HDSIP introduces students to a curriculum consisting of: awareness of health disparities, basic research skills, and community-based participatory research methods. Students are placed at well-established community-based organisations (CBOs) that are dedicated to improving the health of Brooklyn communities	None	2012	2015	4-week summer programme	SUNY Downstate—Brooklyn's only academic medical centre

7.7 / Alumni career pathways – detailed tables

Table 11 / List of the job roles mentioned by BIP alumni when asked about their posts at the time of the survey

Job title at the time of the survey	Role type
Data scientist for a technology consultancy company	Data scientist
Data Scientist	Data scientist
Data Analyst at Public Health Scotland	Data analyst
Data Scientist in Department for Education	Data scientist
Data Scientist at Dementias Platform UK	Data scientist
Policy Advisor in Civil Service	Policy advisor
Information Analyst at Public Health Wales	Data analyst
Software engineer analyst	Computer engineer
Senior Health Scientist at Actryx Ltd	Health data scientist
Research Assistant (Bioinformatics and Computational Biology)	Researcher
Data Scientist	Data scientist
Teaching Job	Educator
Lead data analyst for pharmacy and medicines in UCLH	Data analyst
Data Analyst in UKHSA	Data analyst
Assistant Information Analyst in NHS	Data analyst
Community manager at Data Science for Health Equity	Data scientist
Research Software Technician	Technician
Engineering Data Scientist in Caterpillar	Data scientist
Data analyst	Data analyst
Cloud Engineer in Oracle	Computer engineer
Public Health Analyst in SBC	Health data analyst
Trainee Pharmacist under NHS HEE	Pharmacist
Research Software Engineer	Computer engineer
Solution engineer	Computer engineer
Senior Information Analyst in the NHS	Data analyst

Job title at the time of the survey	Role type
Information Analyst in adult social care	Data analyst
Pharmacist in NHS Trust	Pharmacist
Data Specialist in HIV research	Data scientist
Actuarial Model Analyst	Data analyst
Early Career Health Data Scientist (British Heart Foundation Data Science Centre)	Health data scientist
Software Engineer at Barclays	Computer engineer
Data Analyst in NHS	Data analyst
Executive officer in Civil Service	Civil servant
Sales personnel at Mansa Marketing	Sales personnel
Data Scientist at Leeds Institute for Data Analytics	Data scientist
Junior Data engineer & BI Analyst	Data analyst
Teaching Assistant	Educator
Data scientist at DHSC	Data scientist
Data scientist	Data scientist
Data Analyst	Data analyst
Researcher at Can-survive UK	Researcher
Customer Solutions Manager in AWS	Customer services manager
Clinical oncologist	Doctor
Study Support Advisor at Our Future Health	Study support advisor
Advanced analyst information and insights	Data analyst
Portfolios Delivery officer	Portfolio delivery officer
Software Engineer	Computer engineer
Doctor	Doctor
Training navigator at DATAKIRK	Educator
Research Officer in SAIL Databank/Swansea University	Researcher
Operational associate in Pandora	Business administrator
Pricing Delivery Analyst at BUPA	Data analyst

Job title at the time of the survey	Role type
Administrative officer in HSE	Business administrator
Data and Insight officer	Data analyst
Data Analyst	Data analyst
Associate scientist advisor at Sanofi	Scientific advisor
Software Engineer	Computer engineer
Business Data Analyst	Data analyst
Operations Director	Business administrator
Research Assistant	Researcher
Research Associate	Researcher
Delivery driver	Delivery driver
Analyst in MedPharm	Data analyst
Self Employed	Self-employed
AI Engineer	Computer engineer
Technical Analyst in a software company	Computer engineer

Table 12 / Undergraduate degrees pursued by BIP alumni post internship

Discipline	Area	Russell Group	Funding secured
Medicine, dentistry and health	Pharmacy and pharmacology	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	IT, systems sciences and computer software engineering	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	Mechanical, aero and production engineering	Yes	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical medicine	Yes	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Anatomy and physiology	No	Prefer not to say

Table 13 / Master's degrees pursued by BIP alumni post internship

Discipline	Area	Russell Group	Funding secured
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health data science	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical Medicine	Yes	No
Biological, mathematical and physical sciences	Biosciences	Yes	Yes (Postgraduate master's loan)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Pharmacy and pharmacology	No	Yes (Student Finance England)
Biological, mathematical and physical sciences	Biosciences	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Engineering and technology	IT, systems sciences and computer software engineering	Yes	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical Medicine	Yes	Yes (Student Finance England and NHS)
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health data science	No	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health data science	Yes	Yes (Institutional PhD scholarship)
Biological, mathematical & physical sciences	Biosciences	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Neurosciences	No	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Psychology and behavioural sciences	Yes	No
Medicine, dentistry and health	Pharmacy and pharmacology	No	No

Table 14 / PhDs pursued by BIP alumni post internship

Discipline	Area	Russell Group	Funding secured
Engineering and technology	IT, systems sciences and computer software engineering	Yes	Yes (Unspecified funding)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical Medicine	Yes	Yes (Medical Research Council)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health and community studies	No	Yes (NIHR Applied Research Collaboration)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical Medicine	Yes	Yes (North-South Research Programme)
Biological, mathematical and physical sciences	Chemistry	Yes	Yes (Institutional and industry scholarship)
Engineering and technology	IT, systems sciences and computer software engineering	No	Yes (Science Foundation Ireland)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health data science	Yes	Yes (Wellcome Trust)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health and community studies	No	Yes (UKRI)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Clinical medicine	Yes	No
Engineering and technology	Data Science	No	Yes (Institutional Scholarship)
Medicine, dentistry and health	Health data science	Yes	Yes (Institutional scholarship)
Engineering and technology	IT, systems sciences and computer software engineering	No	Yes (Overseas funding)

Table 15 / Subsequent internships pursued by BIP alumni

Internship name	Duration	Paid/unpaid
10,000 Black Interns	8 weeks	Paid
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Our Lady of Lourdes STEM paid summer internship (student assistant in math department) Summer Studentship with a lecturer at my university (biochemistry lab) Cancer Research UK: Black in Cancer- Host institute London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (cancer epidemiology) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4 Weeks 6 Weeks 8 Weeks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Paid Unpaid Paid
Core20PLUS5 Ambassadors Programme	12 months	Unpaid
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Content Writer Intern – Healthcare Communication Matters Policy and Communication Intern – Faculty of Pharmaceutical Medicine Healthcare Policy, Advocacy and Public Affairs Intern – Hanover Editorial Intern – Pharmaceutical Press All-Editorial Intern – The Guardian 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6 months 8 weeks 12 weeks 12 weeks 3 weeks 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Paid Paid Paid Paid Unpaid
2 internships through 10,000 Black Interns programme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Livingbridge data analysis – 8 weeks + Nationwide software engineering – 8 weeks 	Both paid
10,000 Black Interns – Vertex Pharmaceuticals	8 weeks	Paid
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> National Heart and lung institute (Imperial College London) / Research Assistant Teesside University / Research Assistant 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16 weeks 18 weeks 	Both unpaid
Edelman DXI Market Research Intern	6 months	Paid

7.8 / BIP interns – Summary tables of university group background and nationality at application stage across time

Table 16 / BIP interns’ university group background at application stage across time

	Russell Group		Non-Russell Group	
	Counts	Percentage	Counts	Percentage
2021	22	47%	25	53%
2022	39	49%	40	51%
2023	36	40%	53	60%
2024	39	42%	54	58%
Overall	136	44%	172	56%

Table 17 / BIP interns’ nationality across time

	UK		Non-UK	
	Counts	Percentage	Counts	Percentage
2021	35	74%	12	26%
2022	56	71%	23	29%
2023	35	39%	54	61%
2024	43	46%	50	54%
Overall	169	55%	139	45%

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